

Recommendation for a concept of Blended Learning for dual Vocational Education and
Training in Armenia

Master Thesis

Master of Science in Vocational Education and Training

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Abstract

The aim of this master's thesis is to make a recommendation on how the implementation of dual vocational education and training in Armenia could be optimized by means of Blended Learning concepts. The focus is on various occupations in the agricultural sector as examples. In order to achieve this goal, three specific questions were formulated:

- How must Blended Learning concepts be designed to support dual vocational education in Armenia?
- What conditions are necessary in Armenia's dual VET system to implement Blended Learning in the agricultural VET sector?
- How can Blended Learning be promoted to be accepted in the agricultural sector of Armenia's dual VET system?

In order to answer these questions, nine guided interviews were conducted in Armenia on the topic of Blended Learning with people who are directly involved in the VET system. After translation and transcription, the results were analyzed according to Kuckartz. In addition, 59 students from two Armenian colleges were asked about Blended Learning in a survey.

It became clear that the framework conditions will be pivotal to a successful launch or implementation, with the focus being primarily on the training companies, the infrastructure and the people responsible at the colleges. Furthermore, professional support and standardized introduction are of great importance, especially during implementation. In order to promote the acceptance of Blended Learning, the benefits for all and for the image of the professions, including their knock-on effects, should be demonstrated.

The most important finding of this work is that, even in a setting marked by a lack of investment, the greatest possible benefit from Blended Learning for dual training should be sought with the available resources.

Keywords:

Blended Learning, Dual Vocational Education and Training (VET), Armenia, Agricultural sector

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List of abbreviations

AKIS	Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems
ANAU	Armenian National Agrarian University
BFH	Bern University of Applied Sciences
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GIZ	German Agency for International Cooperation
HAFL	School of Agricultural, Forest and Food Sciences
HEKS / EPER	Swiss Church Aid
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
MAVETA	Modernising VET in Agriculture in Armenia
MoESCS	Ministry of Education, Science, Culture and Sports of the Republic of Armenia
NCVETD	National Centre for Vocational Education and Training Development
SDA	Strategic Development Agency
SDC	Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation
ToT	Training of Trainers
UNICEF	United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund
UPV	Polytechnic University of Valencia
VET	Vocational Education and Training

Recommendation for a concept of Blended Learning for dual Vocational Education and Training in Armenia

1. Introduction

"If there is any one secret of success, it lies in the ability to get the other person's point of view and see things from that person's angle as well as from your own." (Ford, n.d.).

This quote from Henry Ford could be used as a cautionary tale for all international VET projects and therefore also for this Master's thesis, which is anchored in the "MAVETA - Modernising VET in Agriculture in Armenia" project. In this eight-year project, the Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation (SDC), together with other donors, is supporting the Armenian VET system with the development of dual VET programmes in the following agricultural professions: Farmer, Animal Health Specialist, Dairy Technologist, Agricultural Machinery Mechanic, Fruit Specialist (HEKS et al., 2022). The project aims to improve the legal framework for the entire VET system, increase the private sector's involvement in VET and develop curricula for dual VET for the specific occupations, provide further training for teachers and vocational trainers from training companies and ensure the training of teachers and vocational trainers in the dual VET system. In addition to the School of Agricultural, Forest and Food Sciences (HAFL) of the Bern University of Applied Sciences (BFH), which is the main partner of the master's thesis, the Polytechnic University of Valencia (UPV), Swiss Church Aid (HEKS), the Strategic Development Agency (SDA) and the German Agency for International Cooperation (GIZ) are responsible for project implementation (HEKS et al., 2022). The first implementation phase is taking place from 1 September 2022 to 31 August 2025. The main objective is to anchor the dual vocational training system in Armenia and promote rural development in the milk, fruit and nut value chains. The aim is to ensure self-employment as well as the employment of labour in various value chains and to increase income in the agricultural sector.

The Master's thesis is part of project outcome 1 of the systematic project planning (LogFrame). The aim of project outcome 1 is to empower skilled workers and graduates of vocational training in the Armenian vocational training system,

- to apply agricultural and related knowledge, skills and attitudes that are in demand in the market,
- to find or create sustainable, decent income opportunities,
- to contribute to innovative approaches, solutions, products and services on the market (HEKS et al., 2022).

As part of MAVETA, private agricultural businesses and companies will offer new dual VET programmes for the five professions already mentioned in cooperation with state vocational schools. In addition to the learners, the vocational trainers in the training companies and the teachers at the schools must also be trained. This is done through ToT courses (Training of Trainers). The aim is to increase the attractiveness of dual training and the professions themselves through complementary Blended Learning concepts. This is because learning can be organised more flexibly and individually and thus adapted to the needs of the learners. Understanding the difference between dual VET and Blended Learning is key and not very common in the Armenian context.

The aim is to develop a recommendation on how the implementation of dual vocational education and training could be optimised with Blended Learning concepts. The focus is on various professions in the agricultural sector and the colleges that offer them. The definition of Blended Learning for this project will be developed from the existing scientific literature and explained later in chapter 4.1. One difficulty may be that the clear difference between dual vocational education and training and Blended Learning will be clear to everyone involved. This should be taken into account in the definition. The findings can be used for the existing implementation and future vocational training programmes for learners in Armenia. Access to VET is difficult for young people from rural areas, as travelling to school is often an obstacle to regular attendance at vocational school. According to Balayan (2020), a Blended Learning concept for dual VET can help to increase the attractiveness of dual training in agriculture and rural areas in Armenia. Agricultural families, women or disadvantaged people in rural areas could thus be motivated to participate in vocational training programmes, as they can acquire new knowledge and skills without having to spend a lot of time in the classroom (Balayan, 2020).

In order to achieve this goal and to organise the present work, the introduction is followed by various chapters structured by topic. Chapter 2 begins by outlining and delineating the current state of academic research on Blended Learning and international cooperation in vocational education and training. This is followed in Chapter 3 by contextualisation to embed the work, which can be particularly helpful for understanding the framework conditions in the Armenian VET system. After the subsequent definition of the research questions in chapter 4, the method and procedure for data collection are explained in chapter 5. The core of the guideline interviews and the quantitative survey of students are explained in detail. The data analysis according to Kuckartz, including the categorisation, is also explained in this chapter. The next chapter, No. 6, then consists of the results of the previously obtained data. Chapter 7 discusses the results and Chapter 8 concludes with a summary and recommendation for the use of Blended Learning in the dual VET system in Armenia.

2. State of research

The state of research and the existing literature on the thematic focus of this work varies. For this reason, the focus below is on international VET cooperation and the learning - teaching form of Blended Learning.

2.1 International educational cooperation

The Swiss Agency for Development and cooperation (SDC) has been involved in international cooperation for many years. By contributing its experience in vocational skills development, it pursues two objectives: firstly, to improve living conditions by creating new prospects and, secondly, to support the development of national VET systems that meet demand and drive the economy forward (Jäger et al., 2016). Toepper et al. (2021) also confirm the long tradition of cooperation in vocational education and training. An important factor for the increased interest at the dual system of Switzerland was the low level of youth unemployment and the broad support by the population (Jäger et al., 2016). Angles & Lindemann (2019) also cite cooperation between the various partners in dual VET Switzerland as a factor of interest for international cooperation partners. Training in Switzerland often takes place at different locations and management is also a joint task of the federal government, the cantons and professional organisations (Wettstein, et al., 2014). Löwenstein (2022) also emphasises the importance of cooperation between learning locations in vocational education and training, not only in the exchange of information, but constructive cooperation is also particularly central to the innovative further development of dual VET. This knowledge is also repeatedly passed on internationally and adopted in various systems. According to Jäger et al. (2016), the most important thing for the SDC is not to transfer the model of dual VET, but the expertise. This is because sustainable success can only be achieved with the support of everyone, who must recognise the benefits and willingly bring about change in the system (Jäger et al., 2016). This is tantamount to one of the greatest challenges in international VET development: being able to transfer individual elements despite the low social status of VET systems (Toepper et al., 2021). In addition, the willingness of companies in these countries to invest in VET is often low (Wiemann & Pilz, 2020). Another major challenge is the difficulty of communication. These can have both linguistic and cultural causes (Toepper et al., 2021). Peters (2019) also cites successful communication as an important success factor in the transfer and implementation of activities. The English language skills of all those involved often play a major role in this. Of course, fundamental factors such as mistrust or resistance on the part of project partners can also be a hurdle in international educational cooperation (Bohlinger & Wolf, 2016).

Nevertheless, there are also some success factors, one of the most frequently cited being that of the knowledge of context. In order for the measures to succeed from planning to implementation, the conditions in the target country must be known (Peters, 2019). One example of this was the successful pilot project carried out in India between 2008 and 2013. The Indian project director confirmed that the in-depth understanding of the Indian education culture and educational landscape was central to the successful implementation of elements from the Swiss VET system (Probst, 2016). According to Phillips & Ochs (2003), there are various factors that influence the philosophy and ideology of such a process. These are demographic, geographical, religious, linguistic, social, cultural and also philosophical factors. In addition, there are other dimensions such as administrative, technological, economic, political, national or even historical influences, which should always be taken into account in an international education cooperation project. One result of this is the work culture, which in turn influences many sub-processes of such collaborations (Wolf 2017). Furthermore, according to Wolf (2017), the six dimensions of work culture can help to delve faster and deeper into the structures and mechanisms of a particular foreign VET system. By recognising the understanding of work, social security, law, social actors, institutional order and technological development in the target country, cooperation can be made more fruitful (Wolf, 2017). As already mentioned, constant communication between the project partners is also a success factor here, misunderstandings and conflicts of interest can be avoided and, above all, relationships can be built and maintained (Peters, 2019). Finally, organisational factors are decisive for the success of an educational transfer, so responsibilities must always be clearly defined (Peters, 2019). Especially with a large number of project partners, organisational structures and the precise distribution of tasks, including scheduling, are a killer criterion for the sustainable success of a collaboration (Krekel & Walden, 2016). Toepper et al. (2021) conclude in their meta-study that all projects must be tailored to the local labour market. Knowledge of potential geographical differences between urban and rural areas should be known. It is also crucial that the translator is familiar with the culture and conditions of the country. In order to bring about sustainable change, the training of future trainers or teachers is of great importance. Last but not least, the legal and institutional framework conditions should also be known so that a transfer can formally take place at all (Toepper et al., 2021). This is also confirmed by Probst (2016); in the Indian pilot project, a great deal of effort was invested in maintaining contacts with the most important political and institutional representatives. Although they were not directly involved in the project, their consent and knowledge should not be underestimated. Other important findings include an understanding of the economic structures in the target country and knowledge of the infrastructural conditions. Knowledge of digitalisation in the education sector can also be of interest.

In the future, digital solutions will increasingly be used to support communication, cooperation and training (Toepper et al., 2021). With the conscious use of digital technologies, disadvantaged learners can be reached and equal opportunities can be increased through access to education. This also means that knowledge can be made available to a larger number of people in more appealing and cost-effective forms. Nevertheless, new or digital forms of learning should never displace or completely replace the interactions of the people involved (UNESCO, 2023).

2.2 Hybrid forms of learning

Technology-supported learning methods had already arrived in the education system when the coronavirus pandemic struck in 2020. The importance of holistic learning was already great before then, as was the potential for further development of methodological and didactic diversity (Ott, 2011). There are countless forms of learning in the educational landscape today, and these will remain even if the range is reduced to hybrid options (Amenduni & Ligorio, 2022; Pilotto, 2021). Hattie (2012) already showed the added value of digital education technologies in his meta-analysis. Value arises especially when they are used as a supplement to traditional forms of learning and learning settings are designed in this way. This is also because learners can gain control over their own learning process. This Master's thesis therefore only pursues one approach, that of Blended Learning.

2.3 Blended Learning

Blended Learning is a broad term and there is still no unanimous consensus on what exactly is meant by it, or rather the term is attributed to different types of learning and methods (Hassler, 2022; Hassler & Wegmüller, 2022). In addition to the mix of online and face-to-face, the media and methods mentioned are also mixed. The ratio or which approaches are chosen is up to the individual, in principle, anything is possible (Ott, 2011). According to Treumann et al. (2012), however, opinions differ when it comes to the ratio of online to presence. It depends on the target group and the learning content. However, there is a consensus that Blended Learning is a mixture of face-to-face and asynchronous learning that takes place in a dual context in the training company. This is already reflected in the term, which has existed since around the turn of the millennium (Treumann et al., 2012). Various other combinations can be included, whether in terms of methods, social forms or learning phases such as theory acquisition at school versus practical acquisition in a learning company and coaching sequences (Arnold et al., 2018).

The final report of the "Tour de Suisse Blended Learning", which analysed the use and characteristics of Blended Learning at ten Swiss vocational schools, also aimed to determine the understanding of Blended Learning (Weber-Bürki et al., 2024). This showed that Blended Learning is primarily understood as the use of technical tools, a mix of methods and self-organised learning. The networking of learning locations through Blended Learning was mentioned less frequently in the report (Weber-Bürki et al., 2024).

From a learning theory perspective, the Blended Learning concept is anchored in cognitivism and constructivism, as it aims to enable learners to add new knowledge to individual reference points (Treumann et al., 2012; Wipper & Schulz, 2021). Which goes hand in hand with the learning theory of cognitivism, which focuses on the inner mental processes of learning, such as thinking, remembering and problem solving. Learning is seen as an active processing of information in which the learner organises, stores and retrieves new information. This theory particularly emphasises the role of memory and cognitive structures in the learning process. In this way, the information is to be integrated into existing patterns of interpretation (Franken & Franken, 2023). Constructivism, on the other hand, emphasises that knowledge is not passively absorbed, but actively constructed by the learner based on their own experiences and interactions with the environment. Learning is seen as an individual and social process in which exchange and collaboration with others play an important role (Franken & Franken, 2023). This fact also has an influence on the expert or teacher, who prepares the specialist knowledge in such a way that practical learning scenarios are created. They are also responsible for ensuring the smoothest possible transition between the different phases and methods. Ideally, the programme starts with a synchronous kick-off. Expectations and questions can be clarified, and at the end the process and the concept of Blended Learning should be understandable for all participants (Erpenbeck et al., 2015; Wipper & Schulz, 2021). Weber-Bürki et al. (2024) illustrated the implementation of the kick-off using the example of the Wil-Uzwil Vocational and further Education Centre, where at the beginning of a school day all learners receive an input on an area of competence and then work independently on the learning material. The importance of building on previous knowledge and the practical aspects of everyday working life as well as the prevalence of a culture of discussion is considered helpful, as has already been shown from a learning theory perspective (Weber-Bürki et al., 2024). According to Städeli et al. (2021), the AVIVA model can also be used for Blended Learning, as with analogue teaching. The various phases do not necessarily have to be implemented in the specified order. In principle, the Blended Learning approach can be used everywhere when arriving, activating prior knowledge, informing, deepening and evaluating, supported with digital methods where appropriate (Städeli et al. 2021).

For Hassler (2022) and Erpenbeck et al. (2015), the following elements are crucial for successful implementation:

- The Learning process is self-directed
- Teachers serve as support and provide regular feedback for optimisation
- Learning tasks are problem-solving oriented
- Structural aids for individual learning phases are present
- Social learning and exchange opportunities are made possible

The study by Müller et al. (2023) showed that when comparing the effectiveness of learning between different Blended Learning concepts and conventional teaching units over four years, there was no significant difference in student performance.

The same result was obtained in the evaluation of a pilot project at the commercial training centre in Zug, Switzerland (Hassler & Wegmüller, 2022). However, the results indicate that when implementing Blended Learning, specific attention should be paid to the following points: adequate course structure and guidance for students, activating learning tasks, stimulating interactions and timely feedback on the learning process and learning outcomes (Müller et al., 2023). If these prerequisites are met, various advantages are put forward in favour of the use of Blended Learning. The main arguments are often the flexibilisation and individualisation of learning as well as the associated independence of time and place (Machumu et al., 2016; Treumann et al., 2012). Nevertheless, there are also dangers; according to Hassler (2022), the biggest disadvantage is that the Learning content is not processed in the asynchronous phase. This results in the dilemma between refreshing in class and continuing seamlessly. The former undermines the concept of Blended Learning and the latter runs the risk of losing some learners in the process. To minimise this risk, Hassler and Wegmüller (2022) defined the following principles following a pilot project. If these are taken into account when designing the self-study phase, the likelihood of learning activities being developed in a robust manner increases:

- Create a link to the living environment
- Actively shape the learning process and make it visible
- Offer varied learning activities
- Less content, but allow enough time
- Proactive communication
- Accept the learning curve, do not overemphasise failures
- Recognise the teacher's changing role

Despite the possible dangers, the latest developments show that the integration of smartphones in the face-to-face or asynchronous phase of Blended Learning will no longer be an exception in the future, and learning content using gamification will also become part of everyday life (Hassler, 2022).

2.3.1 Using Blended Learning in vocational education and training

The potential and possibilities of Blended Learning for VET are also described by Treumann et al. (2012). The central arguments as to why a Blended Learning concept should be used in VET are self-directed learning and the opportunity to connect the learning process between the different learning locations like college and company.

Figure 1: Blended Learning integrated in dual VET

By promoting media literacy, learners can be motivated to acquire knowledge and skills independently through "learning by doing". Blended learning can also encourage learners to take responsibility for their own learning process not only in the self-study phase. They must always consider their own learning pace, which can be particularly important in practical training (Treumann et al., 2012). Furthermore, Zgraggen (2021) showed in his study on the use of Blended Learning in hospitality training in Australia that the efficiency of teachers could be increased through the targeted use of Blended Learning. The intrinsic motivation of teachers is also important here (Zgraggen, 2021). Gonon et al. (2024) also confirm that teachers at vocational schools are the key players when it comes to technological change and its use in a Blended Learning setting. The creation of an industry-oriented and workplace-related learning offer based on a technological approach in the Blended Learning concept can create added value for everyone (Zgraggen, 2021).

This realisation is also supported by Machumu et al. (2016). In his study on the use of Blended Learning in VET in Tanzania he explains that access to the education system can be facilitated and poverty in developing countries can be reduced. However, for the introduction in such a country to be successful in the long term, a well thought-out concept adapted to the local situation is necessary. Ideally, it should include continuous teacher training, the revision of curricula and the establishment of technological infrastructures (Machumu et al., 2016). Weber-Bürki et al. (2024) also showed that the same conditions for success should be met in Switzerland. In addition to the integration of Blended Learning into the curriculum and a functioning technological infrastructure, teacher development, coaching, feedback and evaluation are pivotal. The SDC also evaluated 16 international projects in education. Eight of these were explicitly in the VET sector and included the incorporation of digital tools (Gröhbiel et al. 2021). The findings are similar to the afore-mentioned ones. The biggest challenges in almost all projects were the lack of digital skills and the lack of access to the internet or infrastructure. In addition, the costs were sometimes too high for some individuals. In one project, the challenge was also to place the learners in companies where Blended Learning was possible. This is because the training companies must be prepared to make the time available to the learners to carry out Blended Learning assignments. Only with the support of the companies can Blended Learning be successfully implemented in a dual VET programme. In the end, the lack of willingness on the part of teachers and the sometimes underestimated preparatory work were once again identified as difficulties (Gröhbiel et al. 2021). These findings were then used to define "lessons learnt" for future projects. The most important of these were that the exchange of ideas in the classroom, including feedback from all participants on the method and content of Blended Learning, would continue to be a key factor for long-term success. It also emerged that small groups are more efficient than large groups, especially when using digital aids.

In order to prevent failure due to financial hurdles or digital skills, the use of existing resources for example social media, is also recommended in an initial phase. In several projects, Facebook was a favourable and efficient solution for communication (Gröhbiel et al. 2021). The survey of students from the two colleges, which is described in more detail later in this paper, showed that various digital tools are also used by young Armenians. Instagram is by far the most popular, with almost 78% of the 59 students surveyed stating that they use Instagram. However, other media such as Facebook, YouTube, Telegram, WhatsApp, TikTok and Viber are also regularly used by young people. A comparison between rural schools and those in the capital of Armenia shows some differences. The biggest difference is in the use of Telegram, which was mentioned five times more by young people in rural areas.

Figure 2: Digital tools used by Armenian students (n=59)

3. Context of the project

As described in chapter 2.1, an understanding of the working culture and the general cultural conditions in the target country is an important prerequisite for the success of development cooperation. For this reason, the most important elements for contextualising and embedding the present work are listed in the following chapters. Findings from the data already collected are included to supplement this.

3.1 Armenia: culture and society

The Armenian people have a long history, but Armenia has only been an independent republic since 1991, having previously been under the communist rule of the Soviet Union for 70 years (Landeszentrale für politische Bildung Baden-Württemberg, n.d.-a). The population of 2.8 million people is homogeneous, with 6.5 % foreigners, and the ethnic minorities are also negligible. The largest of this minorities are the Yazidis, who make up just under one per cent of the population. The Armenian language is spoken by almost 2.7 million people, which makes up 95% of the population (Landeszentrale für politische Bildung Baden-Württemberg, n.d.-b). Despite the low level of diversity, Armenia's democratisation is constantly being put to the test. Be it through the occupation of important political or economic posts by oligarchs, clans, or through the conflict over the Nagorno-Karabakh region, which is not helpful for the country's transformation (Leisse, 2019).

3.2 Private sector

Armenia has repeatedly faced economic setbacks. The transition from a centralised administrative economy to a free market economy has been the biggest challenge in recent years. The formation of monopolies, oligarchic structures and corruption have often been a hindrance (Landeszentrale für politische Bildung Baden-Württemberg, n.d.-c). The conflict over Nagorno-Karabakh and the associated border closures also pose major problems for Armenia's economy. Most recently, the coronavirus crisis hampered trade, as the two largest partners, the EU and Russia, also experienced difficulties (Landeszentrale für politische Bildung Baden-Württemberg, n.d.-c; Swiss Church Aid (HEKS/EPER) et al., 2022). Nevertheless, GDP rose by 5.7% in 2021 and by as much as 12.6% in 2022, making it the eighth largest increase in the world (The World Bank, 2023). Armenia is heavily dependent on Eastern Europe for exports. The three largest buyers of Armenian goods are Russia, Belarus and Ukraine. At USD 847.2 million, Russia in particular has 30 times the turnover of second-placed Belarus and therefore has a major influence on the Armenian economy. Not even the entire European Union can compete with Russia (HEKS/EPER et al., 2022).

The war in Ukraine and the associated sanctions against Russia have therefore also had a negative impact on Armenia's economy (HEKS/EPER et al., 2022). Since 2016, the unemployment rate has stagnated at 12%, with youth unemployment at almost 25% for 2022 (statista, 2023). Two-thirds of job seekers have not completed vocational training (European Training Foundation, 2022). For these reasons, the forecasts for the poverty rate are mostly negative, with a value of 26.5% in 2021 (Asian Development Bank, n.d.).

3.3 Agricultural sector and market situation

The agricultural market situation is therefore also proving difficult, yet the agricultural sector has a major influence on the economy. It accounts for 11.4% of GDP, a good 30% of all working people are in agriculture and 30.5% of exports come from the agricultural sector (HEKS/EPER et al., 2022).

Figure 3: GDP and working people by sector (data from The World Bank, 2023)

Another feature of the Armenian agricultural sector is the large number of farms, totalling 335,000, which have a relatively small average land holding of around 1.4 hectares. This means that individual farms are very limited when it comes to diversifying production (International Trade Administration, 2022). Nevertheless, there are many different farms that are active in the fattening of cattle, pigs, sheep or poultry. However, production is not sufficient for the country's self-sufficiency, and milk production is also subject to considerable seasonal fluctuations and poses a problem (HEKS/EPER et al., 2022). In addition to meat and fish, the cultivation of vegetables, fruit and nuts is also a major branch of the agricultural economy. The focus here is primarily on pome and stone fruit as well as berries and nuts (International Trade Administration, 2022).

The few large farms complain about poorly trained skilled labour, and the small family farms do not have the latest technologies and are therefore unable to produce ecologically and sustainably (HEKS/EPER et al., 2022). With around 1600 processing companies, a large proportion of primary production can also be processed in Armenia. The Armenian state wants to continue to promote the agricultural sector in the future, as it wants to improve economic opportunities for the rural population in particular (International Trade Administration, 2022). This is because the majority of small farmers' household budgets are burdened with debt or loans, which, together with the lack of advisory services, does not lead to any increase in productivity (Balayan, 2022; HEKS/EPER et al., 2022). With the ageing population, the lack of profitability and the past extreme weather events and climate change, this leads to an exodus of the young population. The lack of technical and organisational skills does not make it any more attractive for descendants to remain in agriculture, as there are more attractive jobs in the city or abroad, and so the number of trainees in the agricultural sector is falling every year (Balayan, 2022; HEKS/EPER et al., 2022). Addressing this would be one of the most important measures, as the training of qualified agricultural specialists would lead to more efficient and profitable agriculture and thus make the sector more attractive to young people again (HEKS/EPER et al., 2022). In addition, legislative reforms are being developed to enable access to the Eurasian Economic Union. By increasing quality and safety requirements, confidence in Armenian food is to be strengthened, thereby also increasing production and export volumes (Ministry of Economy of the Republic of Armenia, n.d.).

3.4 Armenia: vocational education and training in agriculture

The agricultural market situation has a direct impact on the willingness of young people in Armenia to undergo training in this domain. In his overview report, Balayan (2020) analysed vocational education and training in the agricultural value chain in Armenia. From this, various fields of action for the future were defined, which are explained in the following chapter. Some of that report's suggestions for improvement have already been implemented in the meantime or have been incorporated into policy. Education has been given a central role in the Armenian government programme. The development of the education system should meet the requirements of socio-economic improvement and the needs of the labour market by 2026 (HEKS/EPER et al., 2022). Examples of reform objectives include

1. Introduction of new professions
2. Introduction and expansion of dual training
3. Training a high-quality workforce that meets the requirements of the labour market (Government of the Republic of Armenia, 2021; HEKS/EPER et al., 2022).

In tandem, the Ministry of Education, Science, Culture and Sports of the Republic of Armenia (MoESCS) launched the Education Development Strategy 2020 - 2030, which includes complete education from pre-school education to lifelong learning and has the following priorities:

- Work-based learning
- Training of trainers
- Cooperation between education and business
- Financing of vocational education and training (HEKS/EPER et al., 2022).

Figure 4: The Armenian education system (CES Chair of Education Systems, 2021)

The legal basis has now been developed and partially introduced, but implementation to date has shown that the formal VET system is still very much school-based and that further measures are needed (HEKS/EPER et al., 2022). In addition to secondary general education, there are also the two vocational training programmes of Preliminary VET, which lasts 1-3 years and can be compared to a craft apprenticeship. The qualification is documented with a diploma from the preliminary VET programme. Intermediate VET lasts 2-5 years and, in contrast to craft training, concludes with a Junior Specialist Diploma (Balayan, 2020).

In the 2020-2021 school year, there were 23 craft schools and 80 intermediate vocational schools, which catered for 32,933 learners (European Training Foundation, 2020a; HEKS/EPER et al., 2022). Of these, just 3% were in initial vocational training and 6% in intermediate vocational training in an agricultural occupation. Only 17 schools (Fig. 5 green dots) offer training in the agricultural sector, 10 of which specialise in agricultural professions. In the practical preliminary schools, the rate is significantly higher at 18 out of 23 (Fig. 5 red dots). Which schools offer an agricultural profession depends on regional needs, and popularity among young people also plays a major role (Balayan, 2020). Massive differences can be seen here: out of 25 modular training programmes at the Middle VET level, just eight are offered throughout Armenia. The four most popular are Veterinary services, Milk and other dairy products production technologies, Wine making technologies and Agricultural economics. Even in the preliminary agricultural VET occupations, only five of the actual 15 occupations are in demand by trainees (Balayan, 2020). The distribution of study places is made by the Ministry and the number is limited to the possible capacity of the training schools. About 50% of the places are financed by the state, the other half is private. However, the public schools struggle to allocate all places (Balayan, 2020). Furthermore, the distribution of schools across the cultivated agricultural area is not even, which leads to different conditions for travelling to school and the aforementioned migration of the young population (American University Armenia, n.d.; HEKS/EPER et al., 2022).

Figure 5: Map of Armenia with all agricultural schools (Middle VET green & Preliminary red) and the cultivated agricultural land (data from American University Armenia, n. d.; own addition of schools)

In addition to the programmes offered by VET colleges, the social actors are also an important pillar in the further development of Armenian VET. The most important actor in vocational education and training is the National Council for Vocational Education and Training Development (NCVETD), which advises the MoESCS on vocational development decisions. The NCVETD consists of 13 experts from the education sector who are active as didactic, methodological or institutional experts in the form of consultants. The social partners are also involved in the administrative boards of the universities and the governing bodies (European Training Foundation, 2020a; HEKS/EPER et al., 2022). One of the most important tasks and at the same time challenges for the future is to organise the matching of professional skills with the demand of the labour market. At the moment, there is no mechanism that can effectively predict the future needs of the labour market. This leads to a constant imbalance between supply and demand on the labour market (Balayan, 2020; HEKS/EPER et al., 2022). The quality of vocational education and training suffers from the existing inefficiency and difficult access, which in turn is due to the geographical origin of the learners and therefore the accessibility of the college. As a result, 41% of graduates believe that their theoretical knowledge does not meet the requirements of their work. As many as 43% make the same statement for the practical skills they acquired during their training (HEKS/EPER et al., 2022). The weak link between the labour market and the training institution contributes to structural unemployment and underemployment. One possible solution to this is to raise the profile of vocational education and training and intensify cooperation between the public and private sectors (Balayan, 2020; HEKS/EPER et al., 2022). However, there are also some challenges here, the biggest of which is motivating and involving training companies when implementing work-based learning. The willingness to take on apprentices is still low due to mistrust in the quality of training and a lack of incentives, which in turn emphasises the importance of cooperation between learning locations (European Training Foundation, 2020a). Although the implementation of work-based learning is regulated in considerable detail in Article 15 "Organisation of vocational education and work-based Learning" of the Armenian Vocational Training Ordinance. Content such as the various forms, dual training, internships or on-the-job learning are defined. Formal matters such as training agreements, protection, payment and insurance for learners are also regulated. The law even includes a recommendation and definition of distance learning:

Distance Learning - a way of organizing basic and supplementary education programmes and a method of synchronous and asynchronous implementation, during which direct or indirect communication between the teaching staff and students (attendees) shall be carried out by means of learning management platforms and telecommunication technologies;

Balayan (2020) additionally recommends that new methods to support for example cooperation between learning locations, such as e-learning tools or learning management platforms, should be used to increase the attractiveness of dual education. In addition, the various stakeholders, especially colleges, should work together to optimise the entire training system. He also sees great potential in the training of teachers to increase the attractiveness of the digital technologies throughout the Armenian education system. Here, too, a proactive exchange of experience in dealing with Blended Learning and digital media across the individual colleges would be very helpful.

3.5 Teacher and instructor training

The responsibility for implementing the various learning situations at the college lies with the approximately 4000 teachers currently working in the two training cycles, preliminary and middle VET. Of these, slightly less than a quarter are in initial vocational training; the average salary is the equivalent of around USD 235 per month, which cannot be regarded as the main reason for employment, as the average salary for the entire population is estimated at USD 400 per month (Balayan, 2020). There are no national requirements for employment as a teacher. A bachelor's degree is often required, with the majority having no practical experience (European Training Foundation, 2020b). To ensure that teachers maintain the necessary skills and can constantly adapt them to the needs of the labour market, exchange between the private sector and teachers should be ensured by the vocational training institutions (HEKS/EPER et al., 2022). This is currently not the case and there is currently no further training system for vocational school teachers. As a result, there are also no compulsory courses that would promote teachers' digital skills (European Training Foundation, 2020b; UNICEF, 2022). The exception was during the Covid pandemic, when 150 teachers were prepared for the use of e-Learning tools via an online course. Previously, between 2008 and 2015, there were various training courses for vocational education teachers organised by GIZ. The 6 to 9-month courses used a Blended Learning approach to teach topics such as lesson design, development of new learning content and support for e-Learning approaches (European Training Foundation, 2020b). A study by UNICEF (2022) showed that 70% of teachers found planning online lessons to be the biggest challenge during the Covid pandemic. The three most cited technical difficulties were poor internet connection, followed by outdated equipment and lack of teaching space. As a result, 34% of respondents would complete an IT / computer skills course. A further 17% would also attend further training in online teaching tools (UNICEF, 2022). Good teacher training would also be important for the attractiveness of vocational training. Digital skills and offers could ensure that young people in remote regions would also opt for vocational training (European Training Foundation, 2020b; UNICEF, 2022).

There are even fewer requirements for practical instructors than for teachers. Instructors in training or on practical courses do not need to have any qualifications other than practical experience. At present, no further pedagogical training or a vocational trainer course is necessary or available (Balayan, 2020). This problem is highlighted in the study of the Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System (AKIS) and a recommendation has been made. According to this AKIS report, the continuous further training of trainers is an important pillar for the success of a dual VET system (AM Partners Consulting Company, 2022). The vocational trainers in the MAVETA project are trained in training-of-trainer courses. One-week workshops are offered on site in Armenia for each of the five professions. Specialists from the School of Agricultural, Forest and Food Sciences at Bern University of Applied Sciences are responsible for the expertise and implementation. The main focus is on learning the didactic and methodological basics so that the learners can also be professionally supported in the company (HEKS/EPER et al., 2022).

3.6 Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System (AKIS)

In addition to the schools with the trained teachers, there are other actors that are central to the development and transfer of knowledge in the agricultural sector in Armenia. A micro-AKIS study carried out by AM Partners Consulting Company (2022) aimed to identify the links and gain a better understanding of knowledge management. The most important stakeholders identified were educational institutions, private agricultural companies, food producers, veterinarians, state institutions such as the ministry and suppliers of inputs such as animal feed. Results also exist at farm level, where it was found that farmers expand their knowledge in part through experienced colleagues or veterinarians, local authorities, private companies from the value chain or via social media (AM Partners Consulting Company, 2022). Despite the networks, the knowledge system is too weak to generate a longer-term and sustainable improvement in productivity and income conditions on farms (HEKS/EPER et al., 2022). Various recommendations for improving vocational training were defined based on the findings:

- Further development of a high-quality vocational training system
- Enabling lifelong learning for the rural population
- Improvement of the curricula in general agriculture, livestock farming and the production and processing of fruit/nuts
- Integrating topics such as business administration and business development into the curriculum (HEKS/EPER et al., 2022).

A report by AM Partners Consulting Company (2022) also highlighted the lack of cooperation between the private sector and vocational schools. In order to be able to support the learning process as often as possible and so that learning can continue after successful completion, the integration of e-Learning is a core element (AM Partners Consulting Company, 2022). Regular short and long-term training courses on general topics or to promote digital skills should enable knowledge to be expanded throughout life. In addition to online distance learning courses and counselling, exchanges of experience can also be linked through visits to successful companies (HEKS/EPER et al., 2022). With the integration of ICT-based delivery of technical and professional content, potential learners in remote areas or with fewer time resources will also be reached in the future (AM Partners Consulting Company, 2022). In addition, systematic career counselling has been carried out in individual vocational training institutions since 2013. The aim of the Armenian government is to introduce a career guidance programme in all 1345 state schools by 2026, thereby improving vocational education and training for the entire population (European Training Foundation, 2022).

3.7 Experience with distance learning in Armenia during the Covid pandemic

The coronavirus pandemic was not only a drastic experience for the stakeholders mentioned in the micro-AKIS study. The education system and schools were also faced with major challenges within a very short space of time. UNICEF (2022) prepared a report on the implementation of distance learning in compulsory schooling in Armenia during the coronavirus pandemic in 2020, which showed that the measures reached 80% of school-age children. A closer look at the data reveals that there are differences in the origin and income of families. The difference in internet availability between urban and rural households is only six percentage points, with urban households being better connected at 86%. The survey of the 59 students in this master's thesis produced a similar result, with higher figures for Internet connections in private households. However, this showed that the urban-rural divide does not exist, as 96% and 97% of those surveyed stated that they had a functioning Internet connection at home. A clear difference of 100% to 70% can be seen when comparing household incomes, with every high-income household having an internet connection (UNICEF, 2022). One reason for this could be the high costs. This is because the average cost of broadband internet is 3% of GDP per capita, compared to just 0.01% in Georgia or Azerbaijan (UNICEF, 2022). The picture is similar when it comes to the availability of digital devices, with only one of two children in rural areas regularly using a computer or smartphone. The difference in income is also greater here than the difference in origin, with 75% of high-income households and 44% of low-income households having such regular use (UNICEF, 2022).

In terms of origin, the survey showed a similar picture to that of UNICEF, although there was no difference between the students of the Armenian colleges. Whether urban or rural, slightly less than 2/3 of students in both stated that they had their own laptop or computer. The figure is higher for having their own smartphone with an internet connection, with a small difference of 93% for students at the capital city college and 87% for students at the rural college.

Figure 6: Students' information channels on existing devices

Following UNICEF's analysis, various recommendations were made to those responsible on how to deal with digital media in the future (UNICEF, 2022). The government is recommended to strengthen the infrastructure and hardware of the education system and to formulate a strategy with local and international partners. The necessary legal adjustments should also be made (UNICEF, 2022). A number of recommendations for action were made for those responsible for schools. The most important of these are to motivate and support teachers in developing new content. The children's environment should also be sensitised to new media (UNICEF, 2022).

4. Questions & operationalisation

Building on the previous chapters, the following questions arise, which are to be clarified by means of the present work:

- How must Blended Learning concepts be designed to support dual vocational education in Armenia?
- What conditions exist in Armenia's dual VET system for implementing Blended Learning in the agricultural vocational training sector?
- How can Blended Learning be promoted to be accepted in the agricultural sector of Armenia's dual VET system?

4.1 Operationalisation of Blended Learning in dual VET Armenia

As already mentioned several times, the clear distinction between dual VET and Blended Learning is central to the understanding of this thesis and their interdependence should be recognised. Dual VET is a system that combines classroom-based education with hands-on work experience, typically through apprenticeships. Learners split their time between learning theoretical knowledge at vocational schools and gaining practical skills in a real-world work environment with a partnering company (Figure 1). Blended Learning can now act as a connecting element between the activities of the two learning locations, but this also presents risks. The key feature of Blended Learning is the alternation between direct contact lessons and self-studying, accompanied by coaching for the students in their self-study periods. It can be useful if digital tools (platform) of communication are available to support students. However, the basic concept of Blended Learning can also be implemented without digital tools if the necessary resources are not available. The figure shows the alternation of the three elements over time:

Figure 7: Three phases of Blended Learning from an organizational view (Lehmann, 2023)

As already recognised, a Blended Learning concept can be integrated into an existing dual VET system in order to reduce possible inequalities due to geographical distances. The asynchronous units promote responsibility and discipline in self-directed learning. In addition to the organisational timeline, a pedagogical timeline or circle can also be created. At the contact lessons important theoretical knowledge and basics are taught by the teacher, and practical approaches can already be used. The cognitivist teaching approach takes centre stage and attempts are made to build on existing knowledge. Tasks for application, observation and consolidation in practice are then distributed and explained. Questions and ambiguities are clarified. In the self-study phase, the tasks are carried out independently in practice, as a trainee in a company or in the own company. This means that what has been learnt at school can then be applied and consolidated independently. The training company can provide support, but is not assigned an active role in the implementation of Blended Learning assignments in dual VET. During the coaching sequences, the teacher is available to answer any unclear questions or additional questions. A digital platform or tools such as Facebook, Zoom or WhatsApp are of course an advantage for this coaching. Back at school, the tasks are discussed and analysed in the contact lessons. Group discussions, plenary presentations, question and answer sessions or other methods of social interaction can be incorporated. Through social interaction and joint reflection, the constructivist learning approach becomes apparent and the new knowledge is actively developed. Experiences are exchanged and then the next learning unit begins.

Figure 8: Three phases of Blended Learning from a pedagogical view

5. Methods

Various methods were used to answer the questions posed in this Master's thesis. At first, an in-depth literature search was carried out to identify the current state of research. The aim of this research was also to embed the thesis in the existing context. A further result of this was the justification of why a Blended Learning concept is the right approach to support the implementation of dual VET in Armenia. This showed that good experience has already been gained with Blended Learning at vocational schools at both national and international level. This start was then followed by two different methods, firstly a guided interview and secondly a written survey. Both were used for basic data collection to answer the research questions and were conducted simultaneously in Armenia for logistical and organizational reasons. The data were evaluated and analyzed using qualitative content analysis according to Kuckartz. The aim was to obtain understanding and acceptance of those directly affected by means of nine interviews and at least 50 surveys at two different colleges. This allowed a recommendation and the requirements for a concept for Blended Learning in the Armenian vocational education and training system to be identified and adapted to the needs.

Figure 9: Methodological approach of the Master's thesis

5.1 Literature review

The literature research was mainly carried out on swisscovery, in addition to documents from the ongoing project that are not accessible to the public. The aim was to provide an overview of the core topics, Armenia's cultural background, agriculture, and private sector, as well as dual vocational education and training. Furthermore, the topics of Blended Learning and international VET cooperation were to be scientifically analysed and defined or narrowed down for the Master's thesis.

There are few documents on the education and vocational training system in Armenia that could be used as a basis for contextualising the master's thesis. For this reason, the existing documents from the call for proposals and the project proposal were all the more important. The curricula of the five agricultural occupations, which have already been developed within the MAVETA project for the future implementation of dual vocational education and training, enabled two concrete examples of the possible use of Blended Learning (Annex A2) to be created. This visualisation, which was as realistic as possible, was intended to help the interview partners understand Blended Learning better. As already mentioned, the state of research on the development of educational content, in particular Blended Learning, is quite broad. The fundamental question of how Blended Learning elements are implemented in dual VET in an international context and how they promote dual VET was investigated. This focussed on the methodological implementation of Blended Learning and existing findings in international VET development. Finally, research findings and general knowledge of international cooperation in VET were included in the contextualisation of the Master's thesis.

Figure 10: Literature search procedure using Swisscovery and project documents

5.2 Guided interviews

A guided interview technique was selected for the interviews with participants from the various institutions in order to generate an appropriate balance between structure and openness (Strübing, 2018). This was not intended to restrict the flow of speech and the breadth of information. Nevertheless, the guiding questions ensured that the most important aspects were not forgotten. The order of the questions was designed flexibly and adapted to the answers to ensure that the interviewees were influenced as little as possible (Schnell et al., 2018). The aim of the guided interviews was to obtain the opinions of the various stakeholders in the Armenian VET system and to identify potential opportunities or problems. The nine guided interviews were conducted with an average duration of 50 minutes and took place between 26 February and 1 March 2024 in Armenia, accompanied by an interpreter who translated between English and Armenian in case of communication problems. The interview was conducted with all participants at the company or school in a separate room. In addition to the interviewee and the translator, a person from the Strategic Development Agency NGO was also present in each case. Beforehand, the interviewees received an overview of Blended Learning (Annex A1) and two examples of a Blended Learning assignment (Annex A2), both in Armenian, by email. This enabled them to prepare for the interview, which mainly focussed on the use of Blended Learning in vocational education and training. Each interview was recorded using a smartphone and the participants signed a declaration of consent (Annex G), which regulates the use of the statements and professional positions for this Master's thesis without mentioning their names.

Table 1 : Interviewees from the Armenian vocational training system and the agricultural labour market

Professional function	Organisation	Background information
Specialist in methodology & didactics	National Centre for Vocational Education and Training Development - NCVETD	Is involved in various projects to promote dual vocational training in Armenia.
President	Armenia e-Learning Network	Also works as a teacher at Brusov State University in Yerevan.
College Director 1	ANAU College in Yerevan	The college is affiliated with the Armenian National Agrarian University (ANAU) and therefore has very good infrastructure.
College Director 2	Etchmiadzin Craftsman State School	The college is located 25 km outside the capital Yerevan. Does not have any digital resources.
Teacher	ANAU College in Yerevan	Teaches both at college and University using Moodle as a learning platform.
CEO	Vanand Agro Farm	Does not work on the farm himself and has his office in Yerevan.
Future vocational trainer (Farmer 3)	Vanand Agro Farm	Manager of a farm with 600 hectares of almonds, which is located 65 km outside Yerevan.
Future vocational trainer (Farmer 1)	Walnut Farms CJSC	Manager of a farm with 140ha of walnuts, which is located 60km outside of Yerevan.
Potential vocational trainer (Farmer 2)	UnderSun Pistachio Garden	Manager of a pistachio farm with 200 hectares of land. Currently still little interest in vocational training.

The interview partners were defined through theoretical sampling (Schnell et al., 2018) and contacted via the project partner SDA. The controlled selection of the sample was chosen because, in the specific context of this study, knowledge of the Armenian VET system and the various perspectives had to be available first and foremost. The small population also played a role in the choice of procedure and method. As many perspectives of the Armenian VET system were to be included as possible.

The guidelines (Annex B) were prepared in advance according to the seven steps:

1. Deepening the research question into key questions
2. Formulation of extension questions
3. Modification of relevance, depending on the interviewee
4. Determine structuring & sequence
5. Appropriation of the guide and creation of a short form
6. Review of the guidelines outside the research field
7. Review in dialogue practice and possible modification (Froschauer & Lueger, 2020)

Figure 11: Procedure for the guided interviews

In terms of content, the guide started with the information phase, where the thesis and the aim of the interview were explained. The confidential treatment of the data was also pointed out and the declaration of consent and enquiry about the recording were obtained and possible ambiguities were clarified (Miosch, 2019). In the subsequent introductory phase, the participants were first asked about their understanding of the documents sent and, if desired, the idea of Blended Learning was explained verbally. This was followed by a few open questions to facilitate the introduction to the topic; the interviewees were asked to lose any inhibitions and talk openly about the subject of the research. In the main phase, the core topics of the thesis were dealt with, primarily focussing on the interviewees' subjective opinion of Blended Learning and its feasibility. In addition, some questions focussed on the topic of the digital implementation of Blended Learning.

In the final phase, the existing responses were organised into sections and reflected upon, with respondents being explicitly asked to add any missing information or statements that had not yet been made and were important in the eyes of the respondents (Miosch, 2019). After the interview, the next steps were explained and thanks were expressed for their participation. Before the guide was used, it was tested on three people: an Armenian employee of HEKS, another employee of the MAVETA project and an employee of the Bern University of Applied Sciences - School of Agricultural, Forest and Food Sciences. In addition, while the interviews were being conducted, the findings were reflected upon and adjustments were made for the remaining interviews.

5.3 Survey

A survey was conducted to ask the learners who will be directly affected by Blended Learning about the idea of Blended Learning. In contrast to the interviewees, they received neither a brief written description nor an example in advance, but were shown the basic idea of Blended Learning in dual vocational education and training directly on site with the help of a 15-minute presentation (Annex H). The PowerPoint presentation was translated into Armenian in advance and the spoken word was simultaneously translated by an interpreter. After the presentation, questions and ambiguities were clarified before the learners began to answer the questionnaire (Annex C) on their own. This was also completed outside of regular lessons in a classroom in Armenia in February 2024, either online or on paper by each person individually. At both schools, the translator, the SDA project worker and two teachers from the respective college were present. The 59 students surveyed (25.4 % girls and 74.6 % boys) were selected using cluster sampling. In this sampling technique, the population is divided into individual groups or clusters, in this study these are colleges. A random sample is then usually selected from these clusters. All individuals in the selected clusters are then interviewed, making this method efficient for geographically dispersed populations. Since no list of the population of all students was available, the costs and effort could be kept within limits. (Schnell et al., 2018). For this reason, various learners with an average age of 17.12 years from different classes in the professions of chef (n = 23), transport specialist (n = 6), wine technologist (n = 15), vegetable gardener (n = 4), meat specialist (n = 2) and dairy technologist (n = 3) were surveyed at two colleges. There were six apprentices who did not state their occupation. Contact with the schools and teachers and the explicit selection of learners was again ensured by SDA's partners in Armenia. The dates of the surveys at the Etchmiadzin Craftsman State School on 29 February 2024, a school outside the town of the same name in the rural region of Armavirs, and the Yerevan College of ANAU on 1 March 2024, which is located in the centre of the capital, were also arranged by SDA.

The survey was anonymised and no conclusions can be drawn about the individual participants. It was also created and conducted using Microsoft Forms, but there were still 27 learners, 23 of whom were in Etchmiadzin, who preferred to answer the questions on paper as they had no access to the internet or did not have a smartphone or laptop. Before being used in the Armenian schools, a pre-test was carried out with the same three people who had already been involved in testing the interview guide. This was to ensure that understanding was present and that the difficulty of the questions was appropriate (Schnell et al., 2018; Steiner & Benesch, 2020). An on-site pre-test with learners was not possible for logistical reasons. As the learners do not speak English, the questionnaire and the answers were translated into Armenian and back into English respectively. This was done by the same translator who was also present at the interviews.

The questionnaire consisted of four open questions, eleven closed questions and one ranking question. In addition, six demographic questions were asked at the end of the questionnaire, including questions about the route to school and transport options. When designing the survey, attention was also paid to the order and possible influence on follow-up questions. In addition to the closed questions on the preference for Blended Learning forms and the technical possibilities, open questions were also asked on the general assessment and motivation of the learners. Nominally scaled answer options were primarily used for the closed questions (Steiner & Benesch, 2020). An animating introductory question, a logical sequence of questions and the manageability of the number of questions are intended to keep the learners' motivation and interest high (Steiner & Benesch, 2020). The demographic questions about the person were deliberately asked at the end and it was mentioned once again that the data would remain anonymous. The aim of the learner survey was to recognise the acceptance and also the possible obstacles or difficulties in the Armenian context. The aim was also to find out how heterogeneous the prerequisites for the use of Blended Learning are.

Figure 12: Survey procedure at the two colleges

5.4 Data analysis of the guided interviews

The guided interviews were analysed using MAXQDA. After automatic transcription, corrections were made in this software and the data were then analysed using qualitative content analysis. The transcription of the spoken interviews was done with the software Microsoft Stream software. Before the text file could be generated, the audio file had to be converted into a video format. Subsequently, the raw file and the transcript in English were inserted into MAXQDA and proofread, all texts spoken in Armenian were removed and the few errors in English were corrected. For further processing, Kuckartz's content-structuring content analysis was used. The process of content-structuring content analysis can be divided into seven steps (Kuckartz, 2018).

Figure 13: Seven analysis steps according to Kuckartz (2018)

The first step of the analysis included three further subtasks. The individual cases, here the interviews, were carefully read through. Statements that seemed interesting or important were highlighted. Furthermore, evaluation ideas and comments were recorded as memos and finally a short case summary was written for each interview. Both were written in bullet points. It was important that no interpretation was made in the case summaries, as the text and the statements made were adhered to as closely as possible (Kuckartz, 2018).

The second phase involved the development of main thematic categories. These were created using a mixed form of deductive and inductive category definition. Two of the categories could already be derived from the research question or the literature review, while the third emerged during the initiating text work in the first analysis step (Kuckartz, 2018). The "Prerequisites" main category contains topics that deal with the framework conditions for launching a Blended Learning concept in the Armenian context in the first place. The category was defined deductively. Weber-Bürki et al. (2024) already showed in the final report "Tour de Suisse Blended Learning" final report that the conditions for success such as the integration of teaching companies, communication between the learning locations, infrastructure or the coordination of Blended Learning with the curricula were mentioned by all participants as standards or prerequisites for the successful launch of Blended Learning. The "Implementation" category of Blended Learning was also generated deductively. Responses were collected here that provide an indication of the actual implementation of Blended Learning. If the prerequisites for implementation are met, factors such as teacher development, method mix, further development of the learning environment, further training or coaching are mentioned (Weber-Bürki et al., 2024). Only the main category of benefits was created inductively, as the interviewees' statements that had not yet been categorised could be combined in it. It contains the statements that indicate a possible benefit of Blended Learning for the various stakeholders in the VET system. Such benefits can be, for example, an improvement in the quality of training or the image of a training programme or college that can be enhanced through the use of Blended Learning.

In the third phase, all interviews were coded sequentially, line by line, according to the rules of Kuckartz (2018). These are as follows:

1. As a rule, units of meaning are coded, but at least one complete sentence.
2. If the unit of meaning consists of several sentences, these are coded as one code.
3. If the introductory (or interposed) interviewer question is necessary for understanding, it is also coded.
4. When assigning the categories, it is important to find a good measure of how much text is coded around the relevant information. The most important criterion is that the text passage is sufficiently understandable on its own without the surrounding text. (Kuckartz, 2018).

In the fourth step of the analysis, all text passages with the same category code were compiled. In the subsequent fifth step, the corresponding subcategories were determined inductively for each main category. The result was presented in a table (Table 2) and the subcategories per main category were recorded and supplemented with a definition and a typical example from the data (Kuckartz, 2018).

Table 2: Subcategories of the content analysis according to Kuckartz (2018)

Subcategories for prerequisites	Short definition	Example from data
Schedule of dual VET and Blended Learning	Includes statements to the interval of the learners' presence at the various learning locations.	First is like clarification of the schedule.
Communication	Includes statements to the communication between the participants (teacher, instructor & learner) of all Learning locations.	So everybody has to go and for him the big challenge will be the relationship between college and company.
Transport	Includes statements to all transport for learners between learning locations and home.	And for this region also because the college is far from the Etchmiadzin. So for taking for them there, they should provide the transportation.
Training companies	Includes statements to the commitment and willingness of training companies to train with Blended Learning.	But the problem is the number of employers, especially in rural countries. Encourage the employers to do it, like to motivate the employers to go for this Blended Learning in dual VET.
Positive mindset	Includes statements to the attitude or positive basic attitude towards "digital" Blended Learning.	And of course we have many teachers that are innovators and they like digital Tools and they are person who can motivate others to follow them.
Legislation about dual VET	Includes statements to the legal basis of dual vocational training.	Yes, I think when the law of VET approved. Maybe the image will change. The colleges should start to think about that because they maybe need some rules, some decisions or some help from higher decision makers or policymakers.
The infrastructure	Includes statements to the infrastructure required for training with a digital Blended Learning concept.	Yeah, hardware, software and infrastructure. And when this one would be or this one is both from a college, the second step would be to show them and how useful e-Learning could be.
Existing resources	Includes statements to all resources and experience that already exist with the use of Blended Learning.	In fact when there was COVID period. And then now with this Blended Learning, we if we want our not depending on or will, we're doing these activities using this Blended Learning. All the colleges with all the professions were doing kind of Blended Learning.

Subcategories for Benefits	Short definition	Example from data
Combining theory and practice	Includes statements to the combination of theory and practice at all learning locations.	If you'd like to have the good specialist, good profession, professional. So it is better to have two day in college and three day working in the employers place.
Image of profession and training	Includes statements to all opportunities to raise awareness of Blended Learning and dual VET.	Maybe also with concepts like that Blended Learning it would help to promote orchardist, dual VET and to promote also that they come to this college.
Improved training quality	Includes statements to the increased acquisition of skills and the final qualification of learners within the framework of dual VET by means of Blended Learning.	So, but working in dual approach it is better because they will teach them the practical part and they will just learning by doing and strengthening the capacities.
Subcategories for Implementation	Short definition	Example from data
Methodological skills development	Includes statements to the deepening and acquisition of methodological competences of teachers and instructors for Blended Learning.	Also the methodological approach. So I can have the educational material, but I cannot deliver this educational material. It also depends the methodology, ...
Transformation of teaching material	Includes statements to the digital and analogue transformation of teaching materials into a Blended Learning approach.	And then it was really difficult to digitise everything to input all this information into the computer.
Courses / Support	Includes statements to the support for the introduction of digital & Blended Learning tools.	And of course there was a need for training of the teachers.

Once the subcategories had been formed, the entire material was coded once again in MAXQDA so that the data could be categorised by case or as desired; this was the sixth step according to Kuckartz (2018). The last step of the content-structuring content analysis was concerned with the actual analysis and visualisation of the results. In this study, attention was paid to the category-based analysis and the correlations between the main categories and subcategories (Kuckartz, 2018). This was because we were interested in which factors are central to the successful use of Blended Learning and which prerequisites must be met for this to happen.

At the end of the process, the results were prepared for the result chapter of this master's thesis and the formulation of a concept for how Blended Learning can be implemented in Armenia. Therefore, a short summary of the findings was written for each case and sub-category to simplify and provide an overview. This ended in a summary grid (Annex J), which can be exported as Excel from the MAXQDA software.

5.5 Data analysis survey

The descriptive analysis of the survey data was carried out using Excel (Annex K). The closed question types were quantitatively analysed and presented in a pie chart. In addition to the responses as a whole, it was also possible to differentiate between them according to college location. A comparison can therefore also be made between learners in the rural region and learners attending college in the capital. Whenever possible, the answers to the open questions were assigned to the subcategories used to analyse the interview data (Mayer, H. O., 2013). This allowed the codes from the content-structuring content analysis of the guided interviews to be reused. If a question or answer could not be coded, the content was analysed qualitatively. A pragmatic evaluation method was chosen for this, whereby patterns in the answers were discussed and then categorised. An internal logic was generated from the individual categories so that the findings could be used in the contextualisation or results section of this paper (Mayer, H. O., 2013). The ranking question of which factors are important for learners to work with Blended Learning, was analysed quantitatively. This was done by calculating the mean value of the ranking for each answer option and then mirroring the scale (Föhl & Friedrich, 2022). This produced the result that the higher the mean value, the more important the factor for the learners.

Figure 14: Evaluation / Data analysis

6. Results

This chapter presents the findings from the guided interviews and the learner survey. The content is organised according to the main and sub-categories of the data analysis. No interpretations are made yet, but similarities or interesting differences or contradictions are already documented.

6.1 Conditions for Blended Learning

A large part of the results relates to the framework conditions which, from the point of view of the participants, must be in place or can have a positive effect on the launch of a Blended Learning concept.

6.1.1 Existing knowledge and experience

When implementing the Moodle platform and digital tools at ANAU College, college director 1 (section 89) and the other teachers drew on existing resources. Some had friends or family members who already had knowledge about the use of digital media. The teacher (sections 27 & 57) also confirms that she is already using individual units of Blended Learning. The students have to solve tasks independently, which are discussed in class. At Etchmiadzin College, too, theory and practice are already linked and the learners are coached by the teachers (College Director 2, section 52). The NCVETD specialist confirms the existing knowledge of Blended Learning. "In fact when there was [the] COVID period. [...] we're doing these activities using this Blended Learning. All the colleges with all the professions were doing kind of Blended Learning" (NCVETD specialist, section 8). As a result, videos and digital media are now being used. The implementation of practical assignments, the presentation of results and the writing of reports are also regularly used in some colleges (NCVETD specialist, sections 27, 82, 98 & 106). The e-Learning network president (sections 67, 74 & 95-96) also confirms that several schools are already using learning platforms, and the majority of feedback is positive. The "Mentor Schools project" demonstrates the advantages of the digital world; online teaching can counteract the shortage of teaching staff. She also sees great potential in cooperation between schools, where knowledge or infrastructure can be shared. In her view, school directors are pivotal to the launch of new concepts such as Blended Learning. As they are very independent and can launch innovative projects easily and independently. The statement from College Director 1 (section 124) shows that there is only limited interest in sharing infrastructure and knowledge and that the schools act as competitors. And in practice, there is little methodological and didactic knowledge that is already available for the introduction of a Blended Learning concept or the support of learners to self-studying.

At Vanand Agro Farm, employees are trained for their daily work in the fields and the knowledge is passed on within the company through training courses. The ability to promote the Learning process with digital media is not available. Furthermore, the independent development of learning assignments would be a challenge for many young people, as some have difficulties with correct writing, describing or solving problems (CEO Vanand Farm, sections 64-67; Farmer 3, section 44).

6.1.2 Positive mindset

The three farmers and the CEO are generally positive about a possible launch of Blended Learning. They see implementation as feasible, as long as the framework conditions are in place and the people are not afraid of change. Even if some working time is lost due to school days and assignments, they cited the good training of specialists as a priority. "Of course we will be missing him [learner] as a labour force but the primary, our goal of us is to teach him everything from A-Z "(CEO Vanand Agro Farm, section 25). The teacher (section 164) and the NCVETD employee (section 120) are also positive about the use of Blended Learning. They are both of the opinion that the most important factor is the teachers. If the teachers recognise the advantages, implementation of Blended Learning can be carried out without any problems; this also applies to the digital tools of a Blended Learning concept. For teachers from the Soviet era, the switch from teacher-centred teaching to Blended Learning including digital media is a huge challenge. On the other hand, the president of the e-Learning network believes that young people are also interested in working with new technologies and methods (section 41). From her point of view, the school director is a key figure in a possible launch (sections 73-74). The two directors interviewed are in favour of Blended Learning and noted that individual elements are already being implemented. It remains important that responsibility, the framework conditions and cooperation with the training companies are regulated (school director 1, sections 38 & 43; school director 2, sections 13-15 & 97). The learners also named a number of factors that would positively influence their motivation for Blended Learning. The most important factor for the students at Etchmiadzin College was the practical work itself, that the knowledge can be put into practice. In addition, there were individual statements about support from classmates/friends or the motivation of the teacher. The students at ANAU College also cited the better link between theory and practice, the support of the teacher and exciting teaching/learning material as motivating factors. When asked whether they would like to have Blended Learning in their education, more than $\frac{3}{4}$ answered yes and less than 10% answered no. A comparison of the two schools shows a difference between urban and rural areas.

Figure 15: Learners' desire for Blended Learning in their training and education

The Learners prioritised six or seven factors that are important to them when implementing a digital Blended Learning concept. An average ranking was then calculated, the higher the number, the more important the factor for successful work with Blended Learning. The ANAU College students also had the factor "Support from employer", as some of them already work in companies. This is only because they are taking part in a dual vocational training pilot project.

Figure 16: Prioritising factors in the implementation of a digital Blended Learning concept for learners at Etchmiadzin College

Figure 17: Prioritising factors in the implementation of a digital Blended Learning concept for learners at ANAU College

6.1.3 Companies

Pivotal to the launch of a Blended Learning concept in dual VET in Armenia is the acceptance and willingness of the training companies for dual VET and also for Blended Learning. The two school directors (college director 1, sections 52, 54 & 132; college director 2, sections 85 & 111) mentioned the low number of companies as a fundamental problem, but the existing partnerships are assessed differently by both. Etchmiadzin College has difficulty finding new partners and the existing ones are only poorly developed. Furthermore, one of the two directors is concerned that the companies will not allow the learners the time for the self-study assignments.

Figure 18: Students believe they would be supported by company with self-study assignments

[...] in his opinion this will not work. This self-study period is a period when the student needs to do something by his own. But when he goes to a company, the company [or] employer would not say OK this is your self study period. Do what you want. There will be some activities according to this employer and the student will be busy doing this apart from thinking about what was his self study process [...]. (College Director 2, section 57).

Three students also expressed this concern in the survey. A further three stated that their training companies would not allow photos or videos to be taken for the documentation and implementation of the self-study assignments in Blended Learning. Nevertheless, most of them stated that they thought their training company would maybe support them in the implementation of Blended Learning assignments. In order to fulfil this expectation, the NCVETD specialist (section 77) would like the training and implementation in the companies to be regularly reviewed. This should ensure that learners are not only deployed as cheap workers but are also given the necessary time to carry out self-learning phases. Some of the training companies also recognise the additional work involved, with three of the trainers interviewed pointing out the importance of guiding the learners. One of them considers the Learning ability of young people at this age to be low, as most of those on agricultural training programmes come from poor families (Farmer 2, section 94).

6.1.4 Communication

Due to the different expectations and the cooperation between learning locations, communication between those involved was seen as an important element. All nine interviewees cited the exchange between teachers, trainers and also learners as essential for the successful training and launch of Blended Learning. "Yes, for sure they [teacher & instructor] should be in close communication and all the topics should be discussed together [...]. If you [learner] get this theoretical part [in contact lesson], it should be practice very soon" (Farmer 3, section 32).

Three of the four interviewees from the field would like the teachers to regularly visit the apprentices at the training company. This should enable them to maintain practical relevance and adapt the theoretical input to everyday working life. Possible lack of knowledge on the part of the teachers is minimised and the training company can influence how the content is linked. Teachers could receive feedback and suggestions for improvement of the theoretical contact lessons from the companies. The interviewed school director 2 (sections 102 & 105) also sees communication as an important factor in maintaining relationships and sharing responsibility for training. This is also confirmed by the teacher at ANAU College (sections 110 & 122), who also sees the potential to increase the quality of teaching and incorporate seasonal aspects in the exchange between all those involved. The CEO of Vanand Farm (section 75) hopes that Blended Learning will not only lead to more discussions in the school context, but also during work on the farm. The learners should discuss assignments, problems, questions and findings with the people on site. The president of the e-Learning Network Armenia (sections 37-39) sees further potential through the launch of Blended Learning with the support of digital media. This will not only make training more transparent, but also simplify communication between the learning locations.

The final argument put forward by three interviewees is the transparent and early communication between the training company and the college in the scheduling of dual training, including Blended Learning assignments. The time and content planning of contact lessons at the colleges and the self-study phases in the companies should take into account the seasonal workload of the training companies.

6.1.5 Schedule of dual VET and Blended Learning

The school director and the teacher at the ANAU College, as well as a vocational trainer, cite a clear agreement between the college and the training company when defining the timetable as a central element for the launch of Blended Learning. Seasonality should be taken into account and learning activities should be aligned with practice. "There should also be some collaboration, cooperation between the employers and the college to have the very clear schedule [...] But the peculiarities of the topic is also very important and also very important the seasonal work overload" (Farmer 2, sections 43 & 50).

When evaluating the three possible interval variants between contact lessons and self-study phases, daily - two days at school & three days at the training company, weekly - one week at school & two weeks at the training company and monthly - one month at school and two months at the training company, the respondents showed different preferences. Nevertheless, three of the four farmers named the daily interval as their favourite. The reason given by all of them was the rapid transfer of theoretical knowledge into practice. The same argument was given by the ANAU College teacher (sections 122 & 124), although she assumed that the farmers would favour the monthly teaching. However, as mentioned earlier, this was only the case for the farmer 2 (sections 43 & 78). His argument was that learners would be available during seasonal working peaks. The school director of Etchmiadzin (section 52) sees this as a danger that learners would not return to school after two months in practice. If they receive a job offer or do not recognise the benefits of the theoretical training, the former is quite possible, as there are too few skilled workers in agriculture.

The 59 students surveyed were also able to choose their favourite time interval for Blended Learning in the survey. There were clear differences between urban and rural areas. On average, more than half favoured the daily interval of dual training with Blended Learning and slightly less than 1/3 weekly theory - practice sequences.

Figure 19: Prioritisation of time intervals for contact lessons - Self-learning phase in a Blended Learning concept of learners by origin

6.1.6 Transport of learners

The teacher (sections 115 & 117) also named monthly block lessons as a possible favourite when choosing the time of implementation, as the travel time of the learners can be minimised depending on this. According to the president of the e-Learning network (sections 84 - 88), Blended Learning offers a great opportunity here, especially if digital media are used. This can reduce the amount of travelling and increase the attractiveness of the training. Both the director of the rural college (college director 2, section 85) and the farmer 2 (sections 53, 54, 65 & 66) argue that their remote locations pose a problem for learners. Neither the school nor the training company can provide transport between the learning locations. Public transport connections are also poor or non-existent.

We are quite far from the city. [...] There is not any internal transportation means in city transportation. So what has been done for finding solution for transportation of the students is that they have [...] created, [...] kind of relationship with the company that is nearby and he [company] provided the transportation, means to bring the students from the Etchmiadzin to here [College] and then back there and then [...] (College Director 2, section 118).

Figure 20: Students' means of transport to school

The vast majority of the actually learners surveyed take the bus to school. The average journey to school takes 40 minutes in the countryside and 51 minutes in the city.

6.1.7 Legislation / Agreement about dual VET

The forthcoming Vocational Education and Training Act is seen by several interviewees as an important milestone for various issues relating to the financing of Blended Learning. The compensation of teachers, which is currently paid per lesson and varies from school to school, is important and must change for Blended Learning. When using a Blended Learning concept, the calculation of the teachers salary must be restructured. Not only the contact lessons should be remunerated as before, but the preparation, supervision and evaluation of the self-study phases and their results should also be part of a teacher's paid work.

Until we have the laws. In some cases, the teacher can say that, [...] my average salary in low. [...]. So I don't want to commit to teaching. [...] And in this case, the director will lose this teacher because there is no other alternative in the region. (NCVETD specialist, section 18)

The college directors (college director 1, section 54; college director 2; section 111) hope for an improvement in cooperation between the learning locations or agreements on what the cooperation should look like. The NCVETD expert (sections 18, 169 & 170) goes one step further with the wish for a standardised implementation of Blended Learning. Furthermore, the conditions of employment between the learner and the training company should be contractually regulated, which is also the hope of Farmer 1 (sections 81-83).

6.1.8 Infrastructure

All three training companies surveyed have a room or are in the process of building one, which can be used by the learners for the realisation or documentation of the Blended Learning assignments. Internet is available at one of the farms (Farmer 1, section 78), can be installed at one if desired (Farmer 2, sections 92 & 93) and is unclear at the third. The CEO of Vanand Farm (sections 68 & 69), in contrast to Farmer 3 (section 100) mentioned that there is no internet on the farm. From a financial point of view, an internet connection is not planned in the near future, as a digital Blended Learning concept would involve high investments. Therefore, in his

opinion, it would be better to start with analogue Blended Learning (CEO Vanand Farm, section 61). The apprentices were also asked in the survey whether they have access to the internet at their training company. The answers support the statements of the training companies.

In order to be able to implement Blended Learning, the director of Etchmiadzin College named two basic infrastructure improvement options. Firstly, the expansion of the premises, including functioning heating. This would allow more students to carry out practical work in class at the same time. Secondly, the acquisition of larger screens to visualise teaching material, which in turn should lead to methodological potential such as improved group discussions. However, there is a lack of money at her college (College director 2, sections 18, 24 & 118). The director of the ANAU College (sections 102 & 122), on the other hand, stated the factors which were important for them to implement digital media and Moodle as a Learning platform. These are a server and the necessary internet connection as well as an information centre that offers courses and support in working with e-Learning media. The NCVETD specialist (sections 122 & 132-137) cites the infrastructure of the ANAU College as an exception. Very few are digitally equipped in this way. In most cases, the server is already missing, which would have to be available for a standardised implementation of digital Blended Learning. The knowledge and methodological skills required for the application of Blended Learning must also be acquired first. Furthermore, laptops, smartphones, computers and internet access must also be available outside of school. The president of the e-Learning network mentioned exactly the same thing (sections 11 & 74), she also mentioned the schools' lack of budget as an obstacle to the implementation of digital Blended Learning.

Figure 21: Internet connection of the students in the training company

Because to implement or to use digital [tools] means they should have computers, laptops, [smartphones] or access to Internet. [...] but as we know that colleges have some lack of digital means, equipment we need. I know that there are many colleges that don't have any classroom with computer. Even there is a computer. It's in the room of directors or [...] administrative staff. (President of Armenia e-Learning Network, section 13)

Despite the lack of money, the teacher (sections 153-155) believes that implementation should be possible in rural areas, provided the infrastructure is in place. In addition to their material circumstances, the students were also asked about their preference between analogue and digital Blended Learning. Half of the 59 students surveyed stated a preference for analogue Blended Learning assignments, slightly more than $\frac{1}{4}$ preferred the digital form and a further quarter had no preference. A difference emerged when analysing the results by college location.

Figure 22: Learners' preference for the implementation of Blended Learning by college

6.2 Implementation of Blended Learning

The main category of implementation of Blended Learning primarily collects responses that provide information on the actual introduction and focus on the time after the launch of a Blended Learning concept. This is also the difference to the conditions category, in which the framework conditions are to be determined before the implementation of a Blended Learning concept.

6.2.1 Support and courses

The NCVETD specialist (sections 11, 18, 109 & 131) recommends that instructors in the training companies should be supported during the introduction and implementation of Blended Learning. Teachers should also be able to attend training and further education programmes. The CEO of Vanand Farm (sections 64-67) mentions the same stakeholders. In addition to the methodological and digital training of the employees of the training companies, the learners should also be supported in their activities. For teachers, he recommends that they receive further methodological and technical training. In some cases, this can also take place at a training company on site. The farmer at Vanand Agro Farm makes the same recommendation.

I mean, one very important thing is also the teachers in the colleges, they should also be retrained [...]. They should also be brought to the farm to see the practice, [...]. Because sometimes practice and theory are completely different things [...]. So that's why the teachers in the colleges are really should be retrained and they should also understand, why it is being done. (CEO Vanand Agro Farm, section 83).

Furthermore, in his view, learners should already be supported by the instructors in the implementation of Blended Learning assignments. In this way, technical problems and questions can already be dealt with on the course (Farmer 3, section 41). At ANAU College, all students and teachers are already undergoing a training programme on the use of Moodle. A specialised group was explicitly recruited for this purpose. In order to transfer Blended Learning into such a digital form, specialists must be employed (College Director 1, sections 95-102). The president of the e-Learning network (section 11) recommends the possibility of several schools working together. In this way, resources can be saved and knowledge shared. She also recommends sharing experiences where possible and motivating other schools to use Blended Learning through success stories. Sharing resources is one of the greatest potentials for launching a Blended Learning concept quickly and with as little additional expenditure as possible.

6.2.2 Methodological skills development

It is possible that various methods and social forms are already being implemented in the colleges in Armenia, says the NCVETD specialist (sections 11, 13 & 18). Nevertheless, more methodological and didactic content should be offered in teacher training and afterwards. Further training for restructuring and the use of Blended Learning should be financially compensated, as the motivation of learners can be increased through a variety of methods and digital tools. Both directors also support the methodological further training of their teaching staff. The teacher (section 138) mentions the methodological diversity of digital implementation, which should be learnt by the teachers first. Four of the nine interviewees mention the support and further training of practical instructors at the teaching companies, who should attend methodological training on how to deal with learners. "So you should have a unique approach to each student to know from what side to approach the student, because they are also different" (Farmer 3, section 60). The same potential vocational trainer mentions that the instructors on site still have to learn how to deal with young people, provide guidance, give feedback, deal with questions or solve problems. Methods should primarily be taught for theory - practice transfer (Farmer 3, section 63).

6.2.3 Transformation of learning and teaching materials

Processing the existing printed documents into digital form was very time-consuming and difficult, said the director of ANAU College (sections 72 & 76). The teacher (section 161) also mentioned the great effort and especially the lack of knowledge as a challenge when digitising the learning content. Both confirm that as soon as the learning platform was up and running and the content was implemented, the Moodle platform provided great added value (school director 1, section 72; teacher, section 161). The NCVETD specialist (sections 72 - 74) would also like to see the digitalisation of all learning content. At present, the remuneration of additional hours depends on the school director. According to the president of the e-Learning network, there is great potential if they are remunerated.

[...], they overcome the first fear or the first step, the next is that they starting speaking to each other [...]. And of course we have many teachers that are innovators and they like and they are person who can motivate others to follow them. (President of Armenia e-Learning Network, section 23).

The start is always associated with a great deal of effort, but as soon as the added value is recognised and the first success stories make the rounds, digital tools find favour. Sharing existing content with other schools can also be a way of reducing the workload of individual teachers when implementing digital Blended Learning (President e-Learning Network, sections 27 & 74).

6.3 Benefits of Blended Learning

The third category, which summarises possible answers to promote a Blended Learning approach in dual VET in Armenia, is that of the benefits of Blended Learning.

6.3.1 Linking theory and practice

The two school directors agree and describe the combination of theoretical and practical training in Blended Learning as efficient (College Director 1, section 43; College Director 2, section 15). The survey of students also showed that more than half see the combination of theory and practice as a major advantage when using Blended Learning. Furthermore, this is also seen as promoting motivation for independent learning. At the rural college, practical training also takes place at school, and Director 2 (sections 13-15 & 52) confirms the use of Blended Learning like assignments. He is convinced that in a dual training programme, companies will not provide learners with time for independent Blended Learning assignments (college director 2, section 57). The NCVETD specialist (sections 27, 77 & 161) also confirms the use of Blended Learning in individual schools in Armenia, using the example of learning diaries and discussions on practical work. She emphasises once again that cooperation between college and company is very important, as practical examples and problems can enrich theoretical lessons. The survey of the learners showed that the linking of practical assignments with theoretical content of the school strongly depends on the respective college and course.

Figure 23: Learners have already carried out practical tasks for the college

Three of the four people from the agricultural sector mention the short interval between theory and practice as enriching, as this allows what has been learnt to be implemented directly and questions that arise in practice can also be discussed in plenary sessions at school. They cite the involvement of the training companies and the exchange with the teachers as beneficial for the training. The CEO of Vanand Farm (sections 53 & 83) adds that the practical knowledge of the teachers is a prerequisite for linking theory. Learners should not only acquire pure knowledge, they should also think about the work steps, actions and their consequences. All farmers confirm that they would support Blended Learning and thus the linking of theory. "For example, the employers will put there [Learning platform] some pictures or write something about the challenges [...] and good experiences can be shared with the others [teacher, farmer, apprentice]" (Farmer 3, section 112).

Among the students surveyed, $\frac{3}{4}$ could imagine taking pictures and videos during the practical assignments, which would later be discussed with the class at school.

Figure 24: Interest of the learners to take photos and videos of the practical work

The teacher at the urban college (sections 92-97) believes that a digital learning platform such as Moodle strengthens the link between theory and practice. This is because learning material and results can be shared more easily and communication with the training companies can be simplified. The president of the e-Learning network confirms the same. She (section 94) also argues that many people in Armenia have practical skills but lack the theoretical background. The introduction of Blended Learning, ideally with digital support, can also reach people in remote areas and make dual vocational training more attractive.

6.3.2 Higher quality of training

Farmer 2 (sections 87-94) confirms that the use of learning diaries and Blended Learning tasks is possible, but that the quality of the training depends on the young people. Two others see a benefit in the written monitoring of practical work in that the work process is reflected on and discussed at the training company and later at school. This should improve the overall quality of the training. The resulting link between the learning locations also ensures improved training (Farmer 1, sections 86 & 87; Farmer 3, sections 26, 68 & 76).

Some students, they can also put there the pictures or attach some video [in the] practical daily report. [...] This report should also be approved by the instructor. Because maybe they [apprentice], she or he wrote like self-evaluation. I did this perfectly and there should be place for comments that the instructor can say [...], no first time you didn't do this perfect. That is why you need to improve this and to do this a second time (Specialist NCVETD, section 92).

Farmer 1 (sections 66-73) also recognises the longer-term benefits; the higher quality of training also means that the quality of future employees is higher, which in turn has a positive effect on the entire company. This realisation is equally important for the two school directors, the training companies must recognise that the training will later result in skilled workers in their sector. They also mentioned that with better resources and materials in the school, the quality of training could be promoted (college director 1, section 134; college director 2, section 108). This is confirmed by the NCVETD specialist (sections 86-92), pilot schools that already use learning diaries and digital media confirm the increased quality of training. The two interviewees from the ANAU College and the president of the e-Learning network cite the permanent availability of learning material in a Blended Learning concept as an important factor in the increased quality of training. The digital implementation of Blended Learning can make the teaching and learning process itself more productive and efficient. Furthermore, the introduction of Moodle has led to greater methodological diversity at the city college.

6.3.3 Image of profession and training

The teacher and the e-Learning network president see great potential in the digital support of Blended Learning in vocational training to make professions and colleges more attractive through an easier access for everyone. Independent learning phases can simplify access, especially for people who live in remote areas.

There are many people who have practical skills, but don't have any theoretical. They can go to college to take the theoretical part. [...] But they can take these courses online [or with self-study]. It will help them and colleges to have additional students. (President of Armenia e-Learning Network, section 94).

A further three interviewees agree that Blended Learning in dual training should be used to show companies that training their skilled workers can bring added value for the company. By involving companies as training institutions in a Blended Learning concept, the current low reputation of dual vocational training should be enhanced. Co-determination and co-design of the training programme can reduce extrinsic motivation, which today makes professions with a poor image and low learner numbers more attractive through financial incentives from the state. Both school leaders and farmers agree that success stories of Blended Learning and qualifications can positively influence the image of a profession, a school or a company. The CEO of Vanand Farm (section 49) cites raising the image of agricultural professions as a major challenge. Blended Learning could be a way of making the professions more appealing to young people and showing them that it is possible to earn money in agriculture with a good education. The NCVETD employee (sections 159-166) points out that the idea and concept of Blended Learning must be understandable for everyone involved in order to create a lasting positive image for training. A clear definition, explanation and introduction would be very helpful and should be recognised as a supplement to dual VET.

7. Discussion

In this chapter, the relevant results presented previously are compared, discussed and interpreted, and the relationship to theory and context is established. If necessary, additional theory is included in the discussion. The aim of this study was to develop a recommendation on how the implementation of dual VET could be optimised with Blended Learning concepts. An attempt was made to answer the three questions presented below as sub-chapters.

7.1 Armenian dual VET supported by Blended Learning

How must Blended Learning concepts be designed to support dual vocational education in Armenia?

A clearly structured concept that regulates the framework conditions for all participants can increase motivation for implementation. Blended Learning should be recognised as an opportunity to improve the transfer of theory to practice in dual training. Understanding Blended Learning and dual VET is a top priority. The differences and networking of Blended Learning in a dual system should be understood by all stakeholders. When carrying out the data collection for this thesis, it became apparent that this is not yet the case and that there is potential for misunderstandings. The self-study phases mean that learners spend less time in the classroom and yet the acquisition of skills is not reduced. As they deepen and expand what they have learnt in the training company with concrete examples. This linking of the two learning locations is the biggest difference between purely dual training and the use of Blended Learning. These findings are consistent with the elements for successful implementation of Blended Learning, self-directed learning processes and problem-solving oriented learning tasks, according to Hassler (2022) and Erpenbeck et al. (2015). They also support the principles of Hassler and Wegmüller (2022), who discuss the reference to the living world and the active design of learning as success factors of self-study phases. Treumann et al. (2012) add the increased motivation through the new component of "learning by doing" in the independent acquisition of competences. The survey of learners on which factors would be important to them in Blended Learning showed that the explanation of tasks was defined as the most important feature at both schools. This supports the statement by Hassler and Wegmüller (2022), who cite an appropriate course structure and student guidance as key to supporting dual VET through Blended Learning. The support of the teacher as a coach or through feedback is considered important by Hassler (2022) and Erpenbeck et al. (2015), as well as by the Armenian learners, and came in third place in the ranking of factors important to them in the implementation of Blended Learning.

The difference in the ranking of the importance of hardware and internet access between the rural and urban college could have arisen from the available resources, the better the equipment, the lower the need, but this cannot be scientifically proven and would have to be examined subsequently. Nevertheless, the digital aspect should not be disregarded when launching a Blended Learning concept, as it offers great potential to support dual VET programmes. The first step in introducing a Blended Learning concept should be to work with existing resources. Depending on the college and location (urban vs. rural), this can also be analogue and therefore without digital tools. There is potential in the collaboration between different institutions or schools; by sharing infrastructures and knowledge, the hurdle of excessive investment can be reduced.

Another benefit of the digital implementation of Blended Learning is the simplified communication between the learning locations and the participants. (Weber-Bürki et al., 2024). It is precisely such standardised and regular communication between the private sector and VET institutions that leads to an improvement in the quality of training (HEKS/EPER et al., 2022). A tool that is suitable for everyone should be selected and the expectations of the various stakeholders should be taken into account. The results of the thesis show further that the responsibilities of the various partners should be clearly defined. There were also several interviewees in this thesis who were in favour of training, further training and support for teachers when implementing a Blended Learning concept. They saw a great need for digital skills in particular, so that dual vocational education and training could benefit from this. This supports the findings of Gröhbiel et al. (2021), who cited the lack of digital skills as one of the biggest challenges in their study. At the moment, there are no courses or training programmes for vocational schoolteachers in Armenia that could remedy this problem (European Training Foundation, 2020b; UNICEF, 2022) although, according to UNICEF (2022) and the guided interviews conducted in this study, the need exists.

Furthermore, a Blended Learning concept should consider the additional work involved in transforming the existing teaching materials. This comment by several interviewees corresponds to UNICEF's (2022) recommendation to Armenian schools that teachers should be motivated and supported in the digital transformation. Zraggen (2021) and Gröhbiel et al (2021) have already demonstrated the importance of intrinsic teacher motivation and increasing efficiency with the help of Blended Learning. This also corresponds to several statements in this paper, which, after a difficult implementation of digital methods, rated the subsequent benefits as very high. In conclusion, it can therefore be said that Blended Learning certainly has the potential to promote dual vocational education and training in Armenia.

7.2 Conditions of Implementation of Blended Learning

What conditions exist in Armenia's dual VET system for implementing Blended Learning in the agricultural vocational training sector?

In order to be able to successfully implement a concept that has been created according to the points listed above, it is essential to take into account the local conditions of the labour and vocational training market. The general context should also be known, in this case the history of Armenia under Soviet rule (Landeszentrale für politische Bildung Baden-Württemberg, n.d.-a). This was reflected in two interviewees' statements that learners should specialise in a very specific activity, such as tree pruning, or that it is easier to train young people without any prior knowledge (Farmer 3, sections 123 & 129). Secondly, that the VET college is only for young people with low skills or from poor backgrounds (Farmer 2, section 94). The legislation also originally dates back to the Soviet era, although Article 15 "Organisation of vocational education and work-based Learning" of the VET ordinance already provides the approach of dual vocational education and training and thus the basis for the use of Blended Learning. Nevertheless, several of the interviewees hope that the new Vocational Training Act will create more clarity regarding the implementation of Blended Learning. This is stated especially with regard to funding and digitalisation. With regard to the latter, the results of this study show that resources and experiences are quite heterogeneous. The implementation of a digital Blended Learning concept currently depends on the school and its possibilities. As a result, digital skills are also developed differently, which, according to the UNICEF study (2022), would be important to make vocational education and training in rural areas attractive. The Covid pandemic has shown that there are still shortcomings in an online Blended Learning approach. In particular, the poor internet connection and the lack of devices represented a major hurdle (UNICEF, 2022). There was a contradiction here in the data collected, the NCVETD specialist (sections 8 & 112) made the statement that during the pandemic all colleges implemented a kind of Blended Learning and continued teaching using various tools. As a result, all teachers are supposed to already be proficient in using digital platforms, but this does not correspond to reality (President of Armenia e-Learning Network, sections 11 & 74; College Director 2, section 52). This is all the more serious because, according to Gonon et al. (2024), teachers at vocational schools are the key players for a digital transformation. This was confirmed by several interviewees. Furthermore, not only the digital but also the practical expertise of the teacher is a key factor in the successful implementation of Blended Learning in dual vocational education and training. This statement is confirmed by Erpenbeck et al. (2015) and Wipper & Schulz (2021), who see the implementation of specialised knowledge in practical examples in vocational schools as a prerequisite for the development of existing thought patterns.

There is still a need for action here in the Armenian context, as most teachers do not have any practical experience (European Training Foundation, 2020b). This lack of practice was criticised by the interviewees. Conversely, most future vocational trainers have no knowledge of didactic and methodological support for learners in everyday working life (Balayan, 2020), so these special circumstances must be taken into account when introducing a Blended Learning concept.

Another prerequisite for being able to use Blended Learning between different learning locations is the basic existence of a dual VET system with two learning locations. As already mentioned in the results, cooperation between colleges and the private sector is not easy and there are not enough training companies, a finding supported by Balayan (2020) and HEKS/EPER et al. (2022). Gröhbiel et al. (2021) already recognised in another international project that placing learners in companies can be a challenge. According to the European Training Foundation (2020a), motivating and involving training companies in dual VET is the biggest challenge in the Armenian system. This is because there is still a great deal of mistrust in the quality of training. This was also demonstrated by one of the farmers 2 (section 94). To increase the commitment of the companies, success stories and demonstrating the benefits of Blended Learning will be helpful. Furthermore, as mentioned in the previous chapter, clear rules such as the time made available by the apprentices or the right to take pictures will strengthen mutual trust. The clear distribution of responsibilities and open expectations as well as the equal treatment of all those involved support the successful implementation of Blended Learning at the companies. Depending on the training occupation and company, seasonal factors can also have an influence on the acceptance of Blended Learning assignments by training companies.

The last condition that can have a positive impact on the use of Blended Learning is the location of the schools. As can be seen in Figure 5, there are some farmed agricultural areas that do not have a college in the immediate vicinity. As was already apparent from the guided interviews, access to the learning locations by public transport is not guaranteed. The survey of students revealed a journey to school of between 40 and 51 minutes. The use of Blended Learning makes it possible to learn independently in terms of space and time and thus to connect rural regions (Machumu et al., 2016; Treumann et al., 2012). A clear concept can positively influence the necessary conditions in Armenia's dual VET system and pave the way for the successful use of Blended Learning.

7.3 Promoting Blended Learning in Armenia's dual VET system

How can Blended Learning be promoted to be accepted in the agricultural sector of Armenia's dual VET system?

In addition to successful conceptualisation and implementation, it is important that the Blended Learning concept is accepted and supported by all those involved in the VET system. A number of points emerged from the interviews that can be used to promote Blended Learning. One of the core arguments is that the implementation of Blended Learning can increase the reputation and acceptance of dual VET, which in turn can have positive consequences in the long term.

The statements of the interviewees support Wiemann & Pilz (2020), who cite the lack of interest of companies in training skilled workers as one of the main challenges, as well as Toepper et al. (2021), who consider the implementation of individual elements with a low social reputation to be a difficulty. According to HEKS/EPER et al. (2022), there is great potential there, as the training of well-qualified agricultural specialists increases efficiency and profitability. This in turn would cast a positive light on dual training. Both were confirmed by the interviewees. According to the International Trade Administration (2022), promoting agriculture and improving economic opportunities is a primary goal of the Armenian state. A core element of this can be the Blended Learning approach (Balayan, 2020). Several people cited the reduction in travelling by learners and reaching the rural region using digital tools as a major opportunity. This argument is supported by international organisations, whereby teachers with digital skills and hybrid learning opportunities in general can result in people from more remote regions opting for VET (European Training Foundation, 2020b; UNICEF, 2022). The opportunity offered by Blended Learning for people with limited time resources, as mentioned by the President of the e-Learning Network (Section 92), was also confirmed by AM Partners Consulting Company (2022). If the circumstances and available resources are taken into account, Blended Learning can increase equal opportunities (UNESCO, 2023).

Another argument in favour of promoting Blended Learning is the potential reduction in poverty, in Armenia, more than 24% of people were living below the national poverty line in 2022 (Asian Development Bank, n.d.). This has already been shown by Machumu et al. (2016), who demonstrated the reduction of poverty through improved access to vocational education and training through Blended Learning in Tanzania.

The least amount of persuasion in favour of the use of Blended Learning is required among the young people themselves, who are interested in the introduction of Blended Learning in their training with an average of 75%. The only difference between the schools surveyed was in terms of analogue or digital. In rural areas (Figure 17), 61% compared to 20% are in favour of analogue rather than digital Blended Learning. In the city, a small majority (39% to 36%) favoured the digital solution. This may be due to the fact that the respondents at the rural College do not have internet access and there are no devices available for digital implementation. Together with the lack of dual VET, it may be difficult for young people to imagine how a digital Blended Learning setting would work. Nevertheless, it became clear that the greatest potential for the use of digital Blended Learning lies in rural areas. Therefore, everyone's concerns should be taken into account when drawing up a concrete implementation concept. To minimise these concerns, success stories should be used to promote the use of Blended Learning and thus dual vocational training. This recommendation from the results of the guided interviews is supported by HEKS/EPER et al. (2022), who, in addition to online distance learning courses and counselling, mention the exchange of experience through visits to successful companies as a means of promoting e-Learning offers. Once again, the exchange and cooperation between the various Stakeholders harbours a favourable and promising potential. Involving the training companies is not only important when demonstrating success, but also during the planning stage, as several interviewees noted. Blended Learning can offer great added value when implementing a dual training programme in terms of time. The reduction of compulsory attendance at the college can be very helpful, especially during seasonal work peaks, and is desired by most companies, which in turn can positively promote the concept of Blended Learning to companies. The practitioners interviewed would also like this seasonality to be taken into account in planning. For this reason, the involvement of training companies in the school's organisation of lesson and timetable planning is seen as important for a positive perception. Having a say is also considered necessary by both Balayan (2020) and HEKS/EPER et al. (2022), as the link between the labour market and training institutions is too weak. Graduates also cite inefficiency and the lack of practical relevance as a problem (HEKS/EPER et al., 2022); here again Blended Learning can support and promote the connection between the two learning locations of dual VET. As already shown by Gröhbiel et al. (2021), the learners surveyed see the use of Blended Learning as an opportunity to increase the quality of training. The majority of interviewees recognise the potential and thus the added value of Blended Learning for the Armenian VET system.

7.4 Challenges and limitations

As already mentioned in the theoretical section, there are several challenges in international VET cooperation, be it linguistic or cultural (Toepper et al., 2021). Of course, there are also various dangers and potential difficulties in the present work, especially in the methodological implementation and interpretation of the data obtained. As mentioned by Peters (2019), the most obvious and greatest challenge is communication in a foreign language. The guidelines and the interviews were written and conducted in English. Despite the involvement of an interpreter who translated into Armenian, linguistic misunderstandings cannot be ruled out, and inhibitions about foreign languages can also lead to answers being distorted. In the learner survey, the questionnaire and the subsequent answers were translated into Armenian and back. These transformation processes could lead to unwanted changes in the results. There is a risk of over-interpretation in the analysis, for example interpretative deduction, if the questions are misunderstood and the quality of the answers contribute to answering the questions of the thesis. A second interpretation error could be significant inaccessibility. Here, in addition to the language, the Armenian culture could also lead to distorted or incorrect results. Finally, there is the interpretation error of hidden meaning if structures or cultural characteristics are not depicted explicitly but would have been central to answering the question. In order to reduce the linguistic and cultural sources of error, understanding was deepened by means of specific questions and the use of an interpreter.

This also allows critical comments to be made on the three quality criteria. The validity can be questioned, as the clear definition and distinction between dual VET and Blended Learning was not always easy. The understanding and, above all, the connection between the two terms was not equally clear for all the people. However, the samples with two schools, one in a rural setting and one urban, as well as the different interviewees provide a good picture. One possible criticism here is that the sample was not drawn at random and the types of education of the learners are not representative of the whole country or the agricultural sector.

The reliability of the survey can be regarded as given. In the interviews, however, it is possible that answers were also given due to social desirability.

Objectivity is ensured in principle, except for the aforementioned, uncontrollable bias that may have arisen from the translation. Despite the proximity to the existing project, the work was carried out completely independently of it and there were no conflicts of interest throughout.

8. Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be said that the objective of a recommendation (Annex D) on how Blended Learning can be introduced to optimise the implementation of a dual training system in Armenia has been achieved. Nevertheless, more in-depth or specific clarifications would still need to be made for concrete implementation at a vocational college, within a training programme or in a further training course. On the other hand, it can be stated that many of the framework conditions are covered when the concept is applied.

During the work, it was recognised that it is not the concept alone that is decisive, but also the people who are involved in it. Specifically, everyone from the college directors to the teaching staff and trainers must be convinced of the use and benefits of Blended Learning. The understanding of dual VET and Blended Learning plays an important role here. Open and transparent communication between all those involved helps. Learners in particular should be given a clear picture of the expectations and possibilities for their training right from the start. The more transparently Blended Learning is introduced into an existing system, the greater the likelihood of acceptance. If the rules are clear and the expectations of the various parties are considered, digital components can also be incorporated. Understanding the difference between analogue and digital Blended Learning can help here, depending on the resources available, it may be more realistic to start with analogue Blended Learning. The different requirements of the colleges, possibly also due to their location, should always be considered.

For the future, this means that as much experience as possible should be gained when launching and implementing a pilot project of Blended Learning. Armenia's entire vocational education and training system could benefit from the experience of success and the hurdles encountered. If Blended Learning becomes established in a school or vocational training programme, this can serve as a motivation or success story for implementation in many other colleges, professions or even companies. An initial implementation can be scientifically monitored and then evaluated and optimised.

The most important finding of this work is that, even in a setting marked by a lack of investment, the greatest possible benefit from Blended Learning for dual VET should be sought with the available resources and that the cooperation of all should be encouraged. Or as Henry Ford once said,

"Getting together is a start, remaining together is advancement, working together is achievement" (Peoria, n.d.).

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10. Bibliography

- AM Partners Consulting Company. (2022). Description and Exploration of the Micro-AKIS in Southern and Northern Armenia to foster Dual VET in Agricultural and related Value-Chains. (Unpublished final report) AM Partners Consulting Company.
- Amenduni, F., & Ligorio, M.B. (2022). Blended Learning and Teaching in Higher Education: An International Perspective. *Education Sciences*, 12 (129).
<https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci12020129>
- Angles, E., & Lindemann, H. J. (2019). Professionalisierung der dualen Berufsausbildung in Peru. In M. Gessler, M. Fuchs & M. Pilz (Eds.), *Konzepte und Wirkungen des Transfers Dualer Berufsausbildung* (pp. 463–513). Springer VS.
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-23185-9_13
- Arnold, P., Kilian, L., Thillosen, A., & Zimmer, G. (2018). *Handbuch E-Learning* (5. edition). W. Bertelsmann Verlag GmbH & Co. KG.
- Asian Development Bank. (n.d.). *Poverty Data: Armenia*. Retrieved 14.09.2023 from
<https://www.adb.org/countries/armenia/poverty#:~:text=Poverty%20Data%3A%20Armenia&text=In%20Armenia%2C%2026.5%25%20of%20the,died%20before%20their%205th%20birthday.>
- Balayan, M. (2020). Vocational Education and Training in Agricultural Value Chains in Armenia: Analysis and the Way Forward. (Unpublished review report) Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation – SDC.
- Bohlinger, S., & Wolf, S. (2016). Zwischen Dynamik und Stagnation. Politiktransfer kooperativer Berufsausbildung als Weg aus der Jugendarbeitslosigkeit in Südeuropa. *Zeitschrift für Pädagogik*, 62(3), 340–357. <http://dx.doi.org/10.25656/01:16762>
- CES Chair of Education Systems (2021). Factbook Education System: Armenia. CES Factbook Education Systems, ed. 1. ETH Zurich.
- Education of the Republic of Armenia, Ministry of Science, Culture and Sports. (2023a). Secondary Professional Education, 0811.07.5 "Veterinary Medicine" Specialty. (Unpublished modul programm).
- Education of the Republic of Armenia, Ministry of Science, Culture and Sports. (2023b). Secondary Professional Education, 0721.08.5 "Milk and Dairy Production Technology". (Unpublished modul programm).
- Erpenbeck, J., Sauter, S., & Sauter, W. (2015). *E-Learning und Blended Learning*. Springer Gabler.
- European Training Foundation. (2020a). *Work-based Learning in Armenia*.
https://www.etf.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2020-10/wbl_factsheet_armenia_2020.pdf

- European Training Foundation. (2020b). *Digital Skills and online Learning in Armenia*.
https://www.etf.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2021-03/digital_factsheet_armenia.pdf
- European Training Foundation. (2022). *National Career Development support system review - Armenia*.
https://www.etf.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2022-07/Career%20Guidance%20Review_Armenia_EN.pdf
- Franken, R., & Franken, S. (2023). Theoretische Grundlagen des Lernens. In: Wissen, Lernen und Innovation im digitalen Unternehmen. Springer Gabler.
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-40822-0_6
- Froschauer, U., & Lueger, M. (2020). *Das qualitative Interview* (second edition). utb.
- Föhl, U., & Friedrich, C. (2022). *Quick Guide Onlinefragebogen*. Springer Nature.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-36291-1>
- Ford, H. (n.d.). *Henry Ford > Quotes > Quotable Quote*. Retrieved 12.09.2023 from
<https://www.goodreads.com/quotes/108918-if-there-is-any-one-secret-of-success-it-lies>
- Gonon, P., Schmitz, M. L., Petko, D., & Consoli, T. (2024). Von der Digitalisierung zur digitalen Transformation. *Transfer. Berufsbildung in Forschung und Praxis* 9(1).
- Government of the Republic of Armenia. (2021). *Plan Programme of the Government of the Republic of Armenia*. Retrieved 11.10.2023 from
<https://www.gov.am/files/docs/4737.pdf>
- Gröhbiel, U., Ghisletta, B., & Büchler, L. (2021). *Digitalization and Inclusive Learning*. Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation – SDC.
- Hassler, D. (2022). Blended Learning, hybride Lehrformate und HyFlex. In D. Bach, E. Haberzeth & S. Osbahr (Eds.), *Höhere Fachschulen in der Schweiz – Herausforderungen und Perspektiven* (pp. 109-123). hep verlag.
- Hassler, D., & Wegmüller, R. (2022). Blended Learning in der Höheren Berufsbildung: Neukonzeption von Präsenzangeboten in eine gemischte Form aus synchronem und asynchronem Lernen in Präsenz und auf Distanz. *#schule verantworten*, 2 (1), 46-55.
<https://doi.org/10.53349/sv.2022.i1.a173>
- Hattie, J. (2012). *Visible Learning for teachers : maximizing impact on Learning*. London : Routledge
- International Trade Administration. (2022). *Armenia – Country Commercial Guide*. Retrieved 11.10.2023 from
<https://www.trade.gov/country-commercial-guides/armenia-agriculture>
- Jäger, M., Maurer, M., & Fässler, M. (2016). *Exportartikel Berufsbildung?*. Hep Verlag.
- Krekel, E. M., & Walden, G. (2016). Exportschlager Duales System der Berufsbildung? In L. Bellmann & G. Grözinger (Eds.), *Ökonomie und Gesellschaft* (pp. 55–70). Metropolis Verlag.

- Kuckartz, U. (2018). *Qualitative Inhaltsanalyse. Methoden, Praxis, Computerunterstützung* (4. edition). Beltz Juventa.
- Landeszentrale für politische Bildung Baden-Württemberg. (n.d.-a). *Geschichte Armenien*. Retrieved 13.09.2023 from <https://osteuropa.lpb-bw.de/armenien-geschichte>
- Landeszentrale für politische Bildung Baden-Württemberg. (n.d.-b). *Gesellschaft in Armenien*. Retrieved 13.09.2023 from <https://osteuropa.lpb-bw.de/armenien-gesellschaft>
- Landeszentrale für politische Bildung Baden-Württemberg. (n.d.-c). *Wirtschaft in Armenien*. Retrieved 14.09.2023 from <https://osteuropa.lpb-bw.de/armenien-wirtschaft>
- Lehmann, R. (2023). *Blended Learning. (Unveröffentlichtes Dokument)*.
- Leisse, O. (Eds.). (2019). *Politik und Gesellschaft im Kaukasus*. Springer VS.
- Löwenstein, M. (2022). *Wege in die generalistische Pflegeausbildung*. Springer Verlag.
- Machumu, H.J., Chang, Z., & Sesabo, J.K., (2016). Blended Learning in the Vocational Education and Training System in Tanzania: Understanding Vocational Educators' Perceptions. *International Journal of Multicultural and Multireligious Understanding*, 3 (2), 20-45.
- Mayer, H. O., (2013). *Interview und schriftliche Befragung* (6. edition). Oldenbourg Verlag.
- Ministry of Economy of the Republic of Armenia. (n.d.). *Agro-processing*. Retrieved 11.10.2023 from <https://www.mineconomy.am/en/page/1327>
- Miosch, S. (2019). *Qualitative Interviews* (2. edition). De Gruyter Oldenburg.
- Müller, C., Mildenberger, T., & Steingruber, D. (2023). Learning effectiveness of a flexible Learning study programme in a Blended Learning design: why are some courses more effective than others?. *International Journal of Education*, 20 (10), <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-022-00379-x>
- Ott, B. (2011). *Grundlagen des beruflichen Lernens und Lehrens* (4. edition). Cornelsen.
- Peoria Magazine (n.d.). *COMING TOGETHER, KEEPING TOGETHER, WORKING TOGETHER*. Retrieved 10.06.2024 from https://www.peoriamagazine.com/archive/ibi_article/2010/coming-together-keeping-together-working-together/#:~:text=It%20was%20Henry%20Ford%20who,historian%2C%20and%20Unitarian%20minister.%20%5D
- Peters, S. (2019). Betrieblicher Transfer beruflicher Bildung: Fallbeispiel Südafrika. In M. Gessler, M. Fuchs & M. Pilz (Eds.), *Konzepte und Wirkungen des Transfers Dualer Berufsausbildung* (pp.312–359). Springer VS.
- Phillips, D., & Ochs, K. (2003). Processes of policy borrowing in education: Some explanatory and analytical devices. *Comparative Education*, 39 (4), 451–461.
- Pilotto, L.M. (2021). *Blended Learning - Innere Differenzierung in der Erwachsenenbildung*. Springer VS.

- Probst, F. (2016). Die Sicht aus Indien – Interview mit G. P. Chandra Kumar, Projektdirektor Indien. In U. Renold & F. Probst (Eds.), *Schweizer Berufsbildungsinitiative in Indien* (pp. 209-215). hep Verlag AG.
- Schnell, R., Hill, P. B., & Esser, E. (2018). *Methoden der empirischen Sozialforschung* (11. edition). De Gruyter Oldenburg.
- Städeli, C., Maurer, M., Caduff, C., & Pfiffner, M. (2021). Das AVIVA-Modell im Blended Learning. *Transfer. Berufsbildung in Forschung und Praxis*, 6 (3).
- Statista. (2023). *Armenia: Youth unemployment rate from 2003 to 2022*. Retrieved 14.09.2023 from <https://www.statista.com/statistics/811634/youth-unemployment-rate-in-armenia/>
- Steiner, E., & Benesch, M. (2020). *Der Fragebogen* (6. edition). utb.
- Swiss Church Aid (HEKS/EPER), Strategic Development Agency (SDA), School of Agricultural, Forest and Food Sciences - Berne University of Applied Sciences (HAFL), German Corporation for International Cooperation (GIZ). (2022). *MAVETA – Modernising VET in Agriculture in Armenia. (Unveröffentlichtes Project Proposal)*.
- Toepper, M., Zlatkin-Troitschanskaia, O., & Kühling-Thees, C. (2021). Research in International Transfer of Vocational Education and Training – A Systematic Literature Review. *International Journal for Research in Vocational Education and Training (IJRVET)*, 8, 138–169. <https://doi.org/10.13152/IJRVET.8.4.7>
- The World Bank. (2023). *GDP growth (annual %) – Armenia*. Retrieved 14.09.2023 from <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.MKTP.KD.ZG?locations=AM>
- Thiévent, R. (2023). *FORSCHUNGSMETHODEN IV METHODES QUALITATIVES* (Unveröffentlichtes Unterrichtsmaterial). Zollikofen Eidgenössische Hochschule für Berufsbildung EHB.
- Treumann, K. P., Ganguin, S., & Arens, M. (2012). *E-Learning in der beruflichen Bildung*. VS Verlag.
- UNESCO. (2023). *Global Education Monitoring Report 2023: Technology in education – A tool on whose terms?* Paris, UNESCO.
- UNICEF. (2022). *Distance Education and remote Learning practices in Armenia*. Yerevan, UNICEF.
- Weber-Bürki, R., Rapold, C., & Ruoss, T. (2024). *SCHLUSSBERICHT TOUR DE SUISSE BLENDED LEARNING*. Eidgenössische Hochschule für Berufsbildung EHB.
- Wettstein, E., Schmid, E., & Gonon, P. (2014). *Berufsbildung in der Schweiz*. hep Verlag.

- Wiemann, K., & Pilz, M. (2020). Transfer research as an element of comsectionitive vocational education and training: An example of factors influencing the transfer of dual training approaches of German companies in China, India and Mexico. In M. Pilz & J. Li (Eds.), *Comsectionitive vocational education research. Internationale Berufsbildungsforschung* (pp. 199–219). Springer VS.
- Wipper, A., & Schulz, A. (2021). *Digitale Lehre an der Hochschule*. Verlag Barbara Budrich, Opladen & Toronto.
- Wolf, S. (2017). International Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) Transfer Project – Theoretical-Practical Experiences of Workplace Training with the Workforce in the Egyptian Construction Industry. In M. Pilz (Edit.), *Vocational Education and Training in Times of Economic Crisis* (pp. 439-459). Springer.

11. Printed Annex

A – Information for interview participants

A1 – General Information about Blended Learning

Blended learning

The key feature of blended learning is the alternation between direct contact teaching and self-study, accompanied by coaching for the students in their self-study. It can be useful if digital tools (platform) of communication are available to support students. However, the basic concept of blended learning can also be implemented without digital tools. The illustration shows the alternation of the three elements over time.

Blended learning is particularly suitable for practical vocational training. A learning sequence consists of the following steps:

- 1. Contact lessons:** Here the important theoretical knowledge and basics are taught by the teacher, with student-activating methods also being important here. There may also be practical demonstrations and individual tasks during laboratory lessons in school. Then assignments for application, observation and deepening in practice are distributed and explained. Questions and uncertainties are clarified.
- 2. Self-study:** The assignments are carried out independently in practice, as an apprentice in a company or in their own company. This means that what students have learned at school can then be applied and deepened independently.
- 3. Coaching:** If anything is unclear or for additional questions, the teacher can be reached as a coach. Depending on the length of the practical period, the teacher may also actively contact the students in order to motivate them and support their learning. A digital platform or tools like WhatsApp are of course an advantage for this coaching.
- 4. Contact lesson with evaluation:** Back at school, the assignments are discussed and evaluated. Experiences are exchanged and then the next learning unit starts.

Preparation

To prepare a course (module) for blended learning, it is important to check the entire content according the following criteria using the template below:

- A. Theory to be presented and discussed in contact lessons: What must be explained by teacher? These are primarily the basic principles and theoretical connections, which students can hardly understand without teacher help.
- B. Practical skills to be learned in contact lesson which need demonstration by teacher/instructor to ensure correct understanding.
- C. New things which can be learned independently. Two things are relevant:
 - Observations in practice, which are then discussed later in contact lessons and help to make the theory lessons more understandable.
 - Theoretical knowledge that students can acquire themselves with a book or on the Internet.
- D. Application and deepening: Which skills can and should be tried in practice. This is the most important part of vocational training.

Structuring learning content for blended learning in VET (full template in Annex)

Topic	Contact lessons		Self-study	
	A Theory to be presented/ discussed	B Skills to be learned with teacher	C New things to learn/ to discover	D Skills to apply and deepen

Based on this analysis of the content you prepare the learning units with alternation between A/B and C/D. Clear assignments must be formulated for C and D.

Coaching

Coaching begins with the formulation of clear assignments and proper introduction during contact lessons. This also includes clear information about where students can get support if they have any questions. Depending on the difficulty and scope, mandatory or voluntary coaching is offered. We differentiate:

- **Group coaching:** Students meet in small groups and discuss their experiences and questions with the teacher. The teacher asks important questions beforehand.
- **Individual coaching:** Students can reach the teacher via social media or phone. Or the teacher visits the students in practice. In dual training, the instructor should take over the individual coaching in the company.

It is important that the teacher informs the instructors about the assignments and that there is regular communication between the school and the company.

Evaluation

The assignments also specify the form of reporting. As a rule, a written report must be prepared on the observations, students own work and the successes and difficulties. It makes sense for the teacher to collect the reports and check them for completeness. However, in terms of content, instead of long individual feedback, various forms of peer-feedback can be more efficient and educational for the students than just a long comment by teacher on each and every detail.

The following are useful forms (see also chapter 5 and 8):

- Discussion of the assignments and findings from the self-study in groups
- Presentation of important findings in the plenary session i.e. on cards or flipchart
- Collecting questions and answering them by peers and teacher in plenary
- Short tests / quizzes / ball-bearing, concept map etc.

It is important to adhere to the principles for constructive feedback.

Digital tools

Digital tools can support blended learning and make it more effective. The luxury version is a digital learning platform where teachers can save documents and assignments, upload videos, etc. and where students can access them at any time. A good platform also allows students to upload their reports there and the teacher to write feedback directly. However, this requires good internet and the students' own laptops/PCs.

Coaching can be made easier if the Internet allows people to communicate with each other using video calls. During the self-study period, for example, one hour each week can be reserved for exchange via video call.

At a minimum, it should be ensured that the students and the teacher can reach each other regularly by phone. It makes sense to agree on clear time windows for this.

Source: Lehmann Robert et al.: Principles, tools, activities and methods for practice-oriented teaching and learning. Chapter 7. Bern 2024, publication planned for May 2024

A2 – Examples of Blended Learning

Example of a blended learning task for the orchardist

BLENDED LEARNING ORDER in Module XX "Scaffold selection"

Learning objective - Module XX / Study result X

Objective of the task / skills to be developed:

You are able to ...

- ... explicate the function of different branches on
- ... execute shape pruning on a young almond tree so that the tree is able to achieve a high yield

Learning sequence:

a) Contact lesson

Theoretical training at school = 1 hours

b) Self-study with Coaching

Practical training at school = 2 hours

Company training = 4 hours

c) Contact lesson with evaluation

Training at school = 2 hours

Problem-solvingorientated learning task:

You are able to carry out shaping work on a young almond tree.

Further tasks:

- Recognize and define the different branches of an almond tree with a sketch
- Carry out formative pruning on a young tree.
- Make a note of the steps you have carried out and the materials you have used.
- Explain your approach to giving shape to a young almond tree.
- Investigate what other options exist for shaping the tree. What methods are used on your farm? Elaborate a summary of each option in a step-by-step approach or with a sketch.
- Finally, take pictures of problem cases (trees where you were not sure how to prune the tree) or pictures of a tree of which you think it is a good pruned example and upload three photos to the [Padlet](#) learning platform without commentary or you send it by mail/whats app to the teacher.

Application task on the farm

Module	XY
Activity in the work process	Determine harvest time and carry out harvesting
Objective of the task / skills to be developed	You are able to determine the exact harvest time of different fruit and nuts ... carry out a professional harvest and implement the required hygiene measures during harvesting of different fruit and nuts ... avoid crop damage and accidents. ... apply health protection measures (e.g. how to carry heavy loads).
Task	Plan your harvest: Describe the fruit to be harvested (variety, characteristics, etc.): Define the time of harvest and justify your choice: How many people are involved and how long is the harvesting period planned? How many boxes of fruits are to be harvested? What are the risks of damage to the fruit during harvesting? How do you prevent accidents and damage to health?
Material	What tools will be used for the harvest?
Required prior knowledge, theory, resources, tools, or checklists for resolving the task	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • You know the growth stage of the fruit. • You can recognise ripe fruit. • You know the harvesting process. Tools: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teaching materials Chapter X • Learning documentation 1st year Number X
How will it be evaluated	Evaluation of the task: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - You present and justify your approach in class. - Your findings and reflections are then discussed in plenary. - Contents of the presentation: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Step-by-step procedure for harvest planning and implementation • Personal evaluation of the task after the harvest

Learning Documentation

Orchardist

Description, Fact sheet (of observation or application)	
Reflection	<p>What went well?</p> <p>What was difficult?</p> <p>What could be done better?</p> <p>Did the planning correspond to the reality?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Persons and duration of the harvest? • Harvest quantity? Quality? <p>Were there any dangerous situations?</p>
Key stones	What are your most important insights?
Further deepening	Any observations/questions/problems to discuss with mentor / teacher in school?

B – Guided interview

Guideline interview on BLENDED LEARNING in Armenia

Interviewer: Translator:.....

Interviewee:..... Job :.....

- Introduce myself (name, institution, work activity)
- Explanation of the role of MAVETA & MSc Thesis
- Presentation of the objectives of the interview
- Obtain written consent for sound recording and use of the data for the master thesis
- Anonymity, if desired:
 - Yes
 - No

Key questions:

1. How would you describe blended learning in your own words?
2. Is the definition of blended learning that you received in the example understandable?

"The key feature of blended learning is the alternation between direct contact teaching and self-study, accompanied by coaching for the students in their self-study. It can be useful if digital tools (platform) of communication are available to support students. However, the basic concept of blended learning can also be implemented without digital tools. The illustration shows the alternation of the three elements over time."

- 2.1 What not?
- 2.2 What is missing?
3. Are the examples of blended learning that you received before the interview understandable?
 - 3.1. What not?
 - 3.2. Why?
 - 3.3. Is something missing?
4. Are the two examples of blended learning feasible from your point of view?
 - 4.1. What not?
 - 4.2. Why?
 - 4.3. What adjustments would be necessary?
5. Are the examples of blended learning interesting from your point of view?
 - 5.1. What not?
 - 5.2. Why?
 - 5.3. What adjustments would be necessary?
 - 5.4. Motivating for the students?
6. How do you generally assess the independent development of competences by learners?
 - 6.1. What motivates you to set such tasks?
 - 6.2. What is difficult about the implementation?

7. Could you imagine the forms of blended learning shown?
 - 7.1. Yes, daily (2 days contact lesson, 2 days practice, 1 day self-study)
 - 7.2. Yes, weekly (1x week contact lesson, 1x week practice including self-study)
 - 7.3. Yes, in blocks (2x months contact lesson, 3x months practical training including self-study)
 - 7.4. No, I can't imagine blended learning.
8. Would you prefer one of the forms shown?
 - 8.1. Yes, daily.
 - 8.2. Yes, weekly
 - 8.3. Yes, in blocks
 - 8.4. No, I can't imagine blended learning.
9. What impact does such blended learning have on your organisation?
 - 9.1. Are there any opportunities?
 - 9.2. Are there any risks?
 - 9.3. What would be important to be in mind?
10. What potential does blended learning have in Armenia's dual VET system? What benefits do you think blended learning could bring in general?
 - 10.1. For vocational training as a whole?
 - 10.2. For the industry / professions?
 - 10.3. For the schools?
 - 10.4. For the learners?
 - 10.5. For the companies / practice?
11. What problems / dangers / challenges do you think are associated with blended learning?
 - 11.1. at school? Teachers no longer paid by the teaching hours?
 - 11.2. in the training company?
 - 11.3. with the teachers?
 - 11.4. with the learners?
 - 11.5. Overall vocational training?
12. What resources are available for the use of blended learning?
 - 12.1. Knowledge of teachers / trainers / learners?
 - 12.2. Access to Internet at school / training companies?
 - 12.3. Are appropriate devices available (PC, laptop)?
 - 12.4. Other digital / social platforms (such as Facebook, Whatsapp, etc.)?
 - 12.5. Possibility of a platform for exchange (learners - teachers - possibly vocational trainers)
13. Where would support be needed for the introduction and implementation?
 - 13.1. When creating the assignments (teachers)?
 - 13.2. During implementation (teachers / vocational trainers / learners)?
 - 13.3. Why?
 - 13.4. In what form?
14. How would you use blended learning...
 - 14.1. as a teacher?
 - 14.2. In the classroom?
 - 14.3. In which modules?
 - 14.4. On which topics?
 - 14.5. How often?
 - 14.6. Reasons why not?

- 14.7. as a school director?
- 14.8. In the classroom?
- 14.9. In which modules?
- 14.10. On which topics?
- 14.11. How often?
- 14.12. Reasons why not?
- 14.13. With what resources (time, hardware, internet connection, curriculum, organisation, further training, etc.)?
- 14.14. Would you invest in new resources?
- 14.15. If so, in what form?
- 14.16. If not, why not?

- 14.17. as a VET trainer?
- 14.18. For which work?
- 14.19. With what resources (time, hardware, internet connection?)
- 14.20. Would you invest in these resources?
- 14.21. If so, in what form?
- 14.22. If not, why not?

- 15. What are the prerequisites for successful blended learning?
 - 15.1. from the school / teacher
 - 15.2. from training company
 - 15.3. from learners

 - 15.4. Would you offer further training as a school?
 - 15.5. As a teacher or vocational trainer, would you attend further training on digital skills or blended learning?
 - 15.6. Would you like an introduction to blended learning?

- 16. How should blended learning be used to make dual vocational training more attractive to young people?
 - 16.1. Which factors are important?
 - 16.2. Can these factors be used for motivational or communication purposes?

- 17. What influences your motivation to use blended learning?
 - 17.1. Positive?
 - 17.2. Negative?

- 18. Is there anything else you would like to say on the subject?
 - 18.1. Was something forgotten?

MANY THANKS for your participation.

C – Survey at colleges

Survey on blended learning among students in Armenia

1. Would you like to have blended learning like the example shown for your training programme?

- Yes
- No
- Perhaps

Why:

2. Have you ever done in practice assignments for the school?

- Yes
- No

3. Which form of blended learning would work in your school? Tick the answers that are possible for you, several answers are possible:

- 2 days contact lesson, 2 days practice, 1 self-study
- on a weekly basis (1 x week contact lessons, 1 x week practice including self-study)
- in blocks (2x months contact lessons, 3x months practical training including self-study)
- No, I can't imagine blended learning implemented in my school.

4. Would you favour one of the forms shown? Please tick only one answer:

- Yes, 2 days contact lesson, 2 days practice, 1 self-study
- Yes, on a weekly basis (1 x week contact lessons, 1 x week practice including self-study)
- Yes, in blocks (2x months contact lessons, 3x months practical training including self-study)
- No, I can't imagine blended learning.

Why:

13. What would be important for you to be able to work successfully with blended learning?
Sort or number the listed points according to IMPORTANCE, in descending order (1 = most important to 8 least important):
- o Explanation of the assignments by the teacher (organisation)
 - o Internet quality
 - o Laptop, PC, smartphone
 - o Support from teacher
 - o Support of the teaching organisation (boss)
 - o Support from classmates
 - o Feedback after the order
 - o Content of the assignments (practical relevance)

14. What advantages do you see in using blended learning in your training programme?

15. What dangers do you see when using blended learning in your training programme?

16. What would positively influence your motivation for blended learning?

17. Other commentary on the use of blended learning.

Personal questions (answers remain anonymous):

- Gender:**
- Female
 - Male
 - Divers

Age:.....

Training programm:.....

Which semester:.....

Time from home to school in minutes:.....

How do you travel to school:.....

Additional questions for dual training:

- 18. Do you think your employer would help you with the blended learning assignments?
 - Yes
 - No
 - PerhapsWhy?

- 19. Do you have an internet connection at your training company?
 - Yes
 - No

D – Recommendation for a Blended Learning concept in the Armenian VET system

Recommendation for a concept of Blended Learning for dual Vocational Education and Training in Armenia

Recommendation for a concept of Blended Learning for dual Vocational Education and Training in Armenia

This recommendation is the result of a master's thesis at the Swiss Federal University for Vocational Education and Training and aims to support the implementation of Blended Learning in dual vocational education and training in Armenia. Various professions in the agricultural sector and the colleges that offer them were selected as examples for development. This was because the master's thesis was anchored in the MAVETA - MODERNIZING VET IN AGRICULTURE IN ARMENIA project.

The most important findings of the work are listed below as tasks. References are made, questions or examples are listed and responsibilities are defined:

BL = Blended Learning

Task	Notes / Questions	Responsibility
Definition & goal of Blended Learning clear for all (incl. integration in dual VET)	Three phases: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Classroom • Self-study • Coaching 	Lead by College
Understanding of Blended Learning must be clear	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Methodological / didactic understanding • Digital understanding 	Lead by College
Clarify the prerequisites for Blended Learning	Integration into the curriculum: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define learning objectives for BL deployment • Define practical work situations for BL deployment • Define hours for BL & learning location • Timetable adjustments 	College & training companies
	Integration Needs of the training companies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordination of theory & BL orders with practice • Time limitations of the training companies • Copyrights to image/video recordings in companies 	Lead college with consultation of training companies
	Be aware of expectations & fears towards BL: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All parties involved 	School directors, teachers, trainers, learners
	Infrastructure/materials: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is available? • Where are investments necessary? 	Lead by College in collaboration with training companies and learners
	Existing digital resources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internet connection • Hardware • Software (learning platform) 	Involving the college and training companies with the learners

Recommendation for a concept of Blended Learning for dual Vocational Education and Training in Armenia

	Legal basis for BL <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financing • Compensation • Responsibilities 	SDA & MoESCS
Conviction of BL	Demonstrate benefits for <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learners • College's • Training companies 	SDA should collect / publish success stories
Offer training & further education	Provide regular offers and explanations/instructions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Methodical - didactic realization of BL at college • Supervision of learners at BL in the training company • Self-study at BL for learners • General handling of tools & aids • Support for problems 	From SDA, state and college
Promote communication	Ensure regular exchange of experience: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Between learning centres • Between learners – College • Between learners and training company • Provide / define standardised communication channels 	SDA with college and training companies
Digitality	Promoting digital possibilities and highlighting opportunities - encouraging a positive attitude	SDA and college

Proceed to generate Blended Learning content (for teachers):

1. Know your students
 - Who are they (characteristics)?
 - Level of students?
 - Digital / Self-study skills?
2. Learning content
 - What should be the outcome?
 - Assessment / Demonstrate competence growth
3. Prior knowledge
 - Current student experience
 - Fundamental, confusing or boring aspects
 - Support through Blended Learning approaches?
4. Design
 - Planning - Point 1 to 3
 - Designing - Design activities, available resources, support & motivate learners
 - Implementing - Tracking learners' activity and give feedback
 - Reviewing - Feedback from learners, industry partners, staff, etc.
 - Improving - Changes for next subjects

IMPORTANT: UNDERSTANDING THAT THE GREATEST IMPACT CAN BE ACHIEVED WITH EXISTING RESOURCES & COOPERATIONS

E – Declaration of independence**Selbständigkeitserklärung**

zur Master-Thesis von Sven Nägeli - 17-256-447

Ich erkläre hiermit, dass ich diese Arbeit selbstständig verfasst, keine anderen als die angegebenen Quellen benutzt und die Daten gemäss den wissenschaftlichen Standards erhoben und bearbeitet habe. Alle Stellen, die wörtlich oder sinngemäss aus Quellen entnommen wurden, habe ich als solche gekennzeichnet. Es handelt sich bei meiner Arbeit um kein Plagiat. Mir ist bewusst, dass eine Zuwiderhandlung die Note F zur Folge hat, dass die EHB zum Entzug des aufgrund dieser Arbeit verliehenen Titels berechtigt ist, und dass allfällige rechtliche Schritte vorbehalten bleiben (Art. 4 und 23 der EHB-Studienverordnung).

Sven Nägeli, Zollikofen - 18.07.2024

12. Digital Annex

The annex is available in digital form.

F – Weekly planning trip to Armenia

G – Declaration of consent

H – Presentation of Blended Learning at colleges

I1 – Transcript specialist in methodology & didactics from NCVETD

I2 – Transcript President Armenian e-Learning Network

I3 – Transcript College Director 1

I4 – Transcript College Director 2

I5 – Transcript ANAU Teacher

I6 – Transcript CEO Vanand AGRO Farm

I7 – Transcript Farmer 1

I8 – Transcript Farmer 2

I9 – Transcript Farmer 3

J – Summary-grid of the interview data

K – Descriptive analysis of the survey data